

D1.3. HOLISTIC IMPACT ASSESSMENTS IN THREE EUROPEAN REGIONS PLUS CO-PRODUCED FIT-FOR-PURPOSE FORMATS FOR DECISION-MAKING FOR WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE

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Description	In this deliverable, we completed a comprehensive holistic assessment of wind energy scenarios for three regions (one each in BG, PT, ES) in two iterations with emphasis on the: 1) cumulative life cycle impacts; 2) relations between local and global impacts; 3) relations between onshore and off-shore impacts; 4) trade-offs between benefits/impacts and 5) environmental feasibility of these scenarios. We provide two types of outcomes. First, to ensure that results are fit-for-purpose, we co-produce output formats with wind energy governance actors (e.g. matrix of policy interactions or a ranking of wind development scenarios). Second, we map environmental impacts geographically according to the defined metrics and outcomes. This task is closely related with T2.4, and its outputs feed into the compass for just and effective wind energy governance (T4.6).

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JustWind4All aims to support the acceleration of wind energy through just and effective governance. We develop knowledge, practical guidelines, instruments, strategies, and training for just and effective decision-making in onshore and offshore wind energy governance. In work package 1, we implement an approach to the holistic assessment of wind energy impacts based on socio-ecosystem metabolism.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADP – Abiotic Depletion Potential
AWE – Airborne Wind Energy
BG – Bulgaria
CAPEX – Capital Expenditures
CED – Cumulative Energy Demand
ECS – Electricity Community Surplus
EEZ – Exclusive Economic Zone
EF – Environmental Footprint (LCIA method)
ESOM – Energy System Optimization Modeling
EU – European Union
GHG – Greenhouse Gases
GLO – Global
GWP100 – Global Warming Potential
HHV – Higher Heating Value
IAM – Integrated Assessment Model
LCA – Life Cycle Assessment
LCI – Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA – Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LNG – Liquefied Natural Gas
MITECO – Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge
NECP – National Energy and Climate Plan
NO_x – Nitrogen Oxides
NUTS – Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OPEX – Operational Expenditures
PNIEC – National Energy and Climate Plan (by its acronym in Spanish)
PV – Photovoltaics
QST – Quantitative Storytelling
RES – Renewable Energy Sources
REE – Red Eléctrica de España
S1 – First-Order Sensitivity Index
SAS – Story and Simulation
SSH – Social Sciences and Humanities
ST – Total-Order Sensitivity Index
STEAM – Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics
WAM – With Additional Measures (Bulgarian energy scenario)
WEM – With Existing Measures (Bulgarian energy scenario)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The energy transition is not only a technical challenge but also a social, political, and ecological one. As wind energy becomes central to Europe's decarbonization strategy, the need for more holistic, context-sensitive, and participatory approaches to impact assessment is increasingly urgent. Deliverable D1.3 of the JUSTWIND4ALL project responds to this need by developing and applying a framework for **fit-for-purpose assessments** of wind energy governance across three European regions: Spain, Portugal, and Bulgaria.

This deliverable builds on the concept of **fit-for-purpose modeling**, which shifts the focus from seeking universally "best" models to selecting and adapting tools that are robust, meaningful, and useful in specific decision-making contexts. In this approach, the assessment method is tailored to the local context, objectives, and stakeholders involved. Robustness here is not defined by predictive accuracy alone, but by a model's capacity to remain relevant under conditions of uncertainty, plurality, and change. This approach is operationalized through **Quantitative Storytelling (QST)**, a methodology that integrates qualitative narratives with quantitative modeling to explore multiple framings, reveal trade-offs, and support deliberation.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH AND WORKFLOW

The project conducted **two complete cycles of QST**, each integrating narrative analysis, modeling, deliberation, and narrative evaluation. These cycles were designed to guarantee that assessments were both technically reliable and socially relevant, grounded in the local context. In each cycle, the first phase involved developing models based on key concerns highlighted in the literature and the project's call for proposals. These results further refined the project's modeling tools. The second phase involved presenting the results from the first cycle to a deliverable process, where narratives were revisited and anchored to specific issues from three case studies. Using the WindSES library presented in Deliverable 1.2 (Madrid-López, 2025), the process enabled exploration of trade-offs, identification of blind spots, and co-creation of insights to support more robust and legitimate decision-making. This approach was used in three case studies targeting different governance issues: in Spain, focusing on distributional justice and spatial environmental impacts; in Portugal, addressing end-of-life strategies for aging wind infrastructure; and in Bulgaria, tackling public distrust, misinformation, and uncertainty in offshore wind planning.

KEY LESSONS FROM THE CASE STUDIES

SPAIN: SPATIAL JUSTICE AND ENVIRONMENTAL TRADE-OFFS

The Spanish case study focused on the environmental and spatial implications of the country's National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) for 2030. Using ENBIOS, the team assessed the environmental impacts of the electricity system transition, disaggregating them into **onsite** (local) and **offsite** (global supply chain). This distinction revealed that while decarbonization reduces local emissions and impacts, it increases upstream pressures, particularly in terms of material extraction and land use. In addition, a **breakeven analysis** examined whether the impacts generated during the manufacturing of new renewable infrastructure (replacing existing fossil fuels) are balanced out over time by the operational emission reductions of the future system relative to today's. The results showed that some impacts (e.g., ionising radiation, energy resource use) are offset within a few years, whereas others (e.g., material resource use) will never be compensated. This challenges the assumption that all environmental costs are temporary and highlights the need for more cautious,

long-term planning. Spatial visualizations also revealed regional disparities in impact distribution, underscoring the importance of integrating **spatial equity** into national energy strategies.

PORTUGAL: REPOWERING VS. LIFETIME EXTENSION

In Portugal, the case study focused on the Cabril wind park, an onshore wind power plant in operation near Viseu in central Portugal. It examined different **end-of-life strategies**, including repowering, substitution, and lifetime extension with either new or reused parts. Using a metabolic perspective, we assessed the environmental burdens, material efficiency, and electricity production of each scenario. The results showed that **repowering** significantly increases electricity output and power density, making better use of land and wind resources. However, it also requires more materials and infrastructure, thereby increasing upstream environmental impacts. In contrast, **lifetime extensions** reduce material use but generate less electricity, potentially requiring additional installations elsewhere to achieve the same electricity production levels. Thus, the results show a trade-off, as each strategy tips the balance toward either **material efficiency** or **electricity production**, but not both at the same time. The case also highlighted the importance of **modular design** to facilitate future reuse and reduce environmental burdens.

BULGARIA: UNCERTAINTY AGAINST MISINFORMATION

The Bulgarian case addressed the challenge of widespread public opposition to wind energy, particularly offshore. Here, the focus was on how **uncertainty** and **mistrust** shape energy governance. The team compared two national scenarios: one with existing energy policy measures and slow developments of wind energy (WEM) and another with additional, more ambitious measures and faster deployments of wind energy, including offshore (WAM). We then assessed the life cycle impact uncertainty for each scenario with Monte Carlo simulations and Sobol sensitivity analyses, identifying the technologies with the most significant influence on impacts and pinpointing where policy efforts should be concentrated. The analyses revealed that the **wind-based scenario performs better across most environmental indicators**, including climate change, fossil fuel use, and ecosystem degradation. Nevertheless, it also involves higher material demands and potential trade-offs between land and water use. At the same time, their results are **the least uncertain, delivering more statistically robust outcomes**. The study shows that openly acknowledging and addressing uncertainties can help build trust for wind power among stakeholders in polarized societies.

CROSS-CUTTING LESSONS

MODELING MUST BE PURPOSE-DRIVEN AND REFLEXIVE. Rather than seeking universally “best” models, assessments must be aligned with the **specific purposes** and **contexts** of decision-making. This includes recognizing that models are not neutral; they embed assumptions, reflect value systems, and shape the narratives they are meant to inform. The use of QST across all three cases demonstrated how modeling can support **deliberation, reflection, and co-production**, rather than simply optimization and prediction.

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT MUST REFLECT SPATIAL, TEMPORAL, AND SOCIAL DIMENSIONS.

Traditional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methods often rely on static inventories and generalized assumptions. To be fit for purpose, LCA must be **contextualized**, as demonstrated in Spain and Bulgaria, where inventories were adapted to regional energy mixes and infrastructure lifetimes. The ENBIOS tool is designed to provide this contextualization. By disaggregating impacts into onsite and offsite categories, LCA results can be easier to interpret and support more equitable planning.

Integrating LCA with other methods (e.g., metabolic analysis, sensitivity analysis) also improved robustness and relevance.

TRADE-OFFS ARE INHERENT AND MUST BE MADE VISIBLE. Energy transitions inevitably involve **trade-offs**. We observe challenges between environmental goals, technological feasibility, social acceptance, and spatial equity. These trade-offs are often hidden in dominant policy narratives or obscured by aggregated metrics. Valuation exercises are essential for surfacing these tensions and enabling more informed, inclusive decision-making.

ENVIRONMENTAL FEASIBILITY IS SCALE-DEPENDENT AND MULTIDIMENSIONAL. Solutions that appear feasible at the national level may have major drawbacks on the regional or local scale. For example, Spain's PNIEC projects a doubling of wind capacity by 2030, but regional analyses show that some communities will bear disproportionate burdens. Similarly, repowering in Portugal is more beneficial at the system level than at the turbine level. Environmental feasibility must also consider **non-carbon impacts** such as land use, water consumption, and material demand, and recognize that some impacts may be **irreversible** or **non-compensable**.

LOCAL–GLOBAL RELATIONS MUST BE ADDRESSED. Wind energy reduces emissions at the point of generation but introduces new pressures elsewhere, particularly in the **global supply chains** for materials and components. These offsite impacts are often invisible in national assessments but raise serious questions about **distributional justice** and **global equity**. A just transition must account for these transboundary effects and promote ethical sourcing, fair trade, and international cooperation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The energy transition presents not only technical challenges but also significant social and political ones. As wind energy becomes central to Europe’s decarbonization efforts, there is an increasing need to evaluate its social and environmental impacts comprehensively. However, traditional modeling methods often struggle to reflect the complexity of these transitions and the real-world connections they entail. Conventional policy models primarily depend on predictive mathematical approaches, which excel at techno-economic optimization but fall short in addressing the uncertainties, value-based trade-offs, and specific contextual factors inherent in socio-ecological systems (Campos et al., 2024; de Tomás Pascual et al., 2025).

In response, the concept of fit-for-purpose modeling has gained traction in sustainability science and energy governance (Selin et al., 2023). Rather than seeking the “best” model in abstract terms, fit-for-purpose approaches emphasize the alignment between modeling tools, stakeholder needs, and the specific questions at hand. This perspective recognizes that different purposes—such as informing infrastructure planning, supporting deliberation, or revealing distributional injustices—require different types of models, metrics, and formats. Robustness, in this context, is not about predictive accuracy alone but about the capacity of models to remain useful and meaningful under conditions of uncertainty, plurality, and change.

This deliverable contributes to this evolving field by exploring how holistic impact assessments and co-produced modeling formats can support more just and effective wind energy governance. Drawing on the methodology of Quantitative Storytelling (QST), we integrate qualitative narratives with quantitative assessments to assess the viability and feasibility of wind energy transitions in three European regions: Spain, Portugal, and Bulgaria. In Spain, the focus is on distributional justice and the spatial allocation of environmental impacts; in Portugal, the challenge lies in repowering aging infrastructure while maximizing land and material efficiency; and in Bulgaria, the emphasis is on managing uncertainty and fostering social acceptance through transparent scenario analysis. Each case study illustrates how fit-for-purpose modeling can help navigate key barriers ranging from spatial justice and infrastructure repowering to uncertainty and social acceptance while also revealing the trade-offs and blind spots of dominant policy narratives.

1.1 OVERCOMING BARRIERS

Despite its promise, the implementation of wind energy in Europe continues to face a range of persistent barriers. These span administrative, technical, economic, and social dimensions. Complex permitting procedures, fragmented governance, and a lack of transparency delay project approvals (Banasiak et al., 2022; Iglesias et al., 2011). Challenges persist with emerging technologies such as floating and airborne wind, grid integration, and skilled labor shortages (Cortese, 2019a; Georgilakis, 2008a; Subbulakshmi et al., 2022a). Economic constraints include high upfront costs, unstable support schemes, and market dominance by conventional utilities (Dhingra et al., 2022; Diógenes et al., 2020).

Social acceptance remains a critical barrier, often driven by perceptions of unfair distribution of costs and benefits, ecological concerns, and lack of local participation (Zografos & Martinez-Alier, 2009). These issues are unevenly distributed, fueling local opposition and planning conflicts (Duarte et al., 2022; Lloret et al., 2022). Despite these challenges, wind energy offers significant environmental and community benefits, including reduced emissions, lower water use, and opportunities for community ownership (Aitken, 2010; International Energy Agency - IEA, 2016; Oteri, 2012).

The three case studies presented in this deliverable illustrate how these general barriers manifest in specific regional contexts. In Spain, we highlight the challenge of the uneven spatial distribution of environmental impacts and benefits. Wind infrastructure is often concentrated in rural areas, while the benefits, such as electricity and economic returns, are distributed elsewhere. This spatial mismatch raises concerns about distributional justice and contributes to local resistance. In addition, the transition also has a global dimension, as the infrastructure deployed in Spain depends on resource extraction and socio-ecological burdens abroad, a factor often overlooked in local debates as well as in national and regional policies. The Spanish case study addresses these issues by using spatially explicit metrics to visualize and assess the geographical allocation of burdens and benefits, aiming to inform more equitable planning.

In Portugal, we address the barrier posed by the limited understanding of the end-of-life broader trade-offs beyond techno-economic considerations. This challenge is particularly pressing given that Portugal has one of the oldest wind fleets in Europe. Decisions around repowering, life extension, or substitution involve compromises between material use, land occupation, and electricity generation potential. The Portuguese case study explores these trade-offs through a combined life cycle and metabolic assessment of different end-of-life scenarios, highlighting the need for context-specific strategies that balance environmental efficiency with infrastructure reuse.

In Bulgaria, we face the challenge of a widespread lack of social acceptance that extends beyond local issues with installations. Despite high wind potential in the Black Sea, offshore development has been stalled by public opposition, misinformation, and institutional inertia. The Bulgarian case study explores how evidence-based policy can influence public perceptions and falsely enhance legitimacy. It demonstrates how embracing the uncertainty behind modeling in scenario analysis can help surface stakeholder concerns and clarify trade-offs.

2 (CO)PRODUCING FIT-FOR-PURPOSE ANALYSES

2.1 DEFINING ROBUST MODELS AS THOSE FIT FOR PURPOSE

Changes related to the energy transition seem to be progressing faster than for other societal challenges, such as food provisioning (Geels et al., 2023). However, despite its relevance and speed, we have a long way to go to understand its social and environmental impacts (Köhler et al., 2019). Because of its (super)wickedness, there is a call to find *robust* (as opposed to *best*) methods of assessment for energy transitions. However, the definition of robust is not straightforward and entails several complexities (Giampietro, 2014). In short, we could argue that a robust method is fit for “a” purpose. However, the variety of ways in which a *purpose* is defined and what *fit* means makes this definition challenging. In the context of modeling, robustness is frequently defined in terms of the modeling capacity to adapt to multiple dimensions and uncertainties (Rodriguez-Matas et al., 2024) and/or their capacity to embrace key sensitivities (Vögele et al., 2023).

In terms of modeling capacity, energy system optimization modeling (ESOM) and life cycle assessment (LCA) have been key in assessing and understanding the techno-economic and environmental aspects of the energy transition. ESOMs are models used to find techno-economically feasible energy system configurations under additional normative constraints, like for example, a given emission reduction. LCA is a framework for the modeling of the value chain of products and services, used in the framework of the energy transition, mostly to assess the development of infrastructure at different levels. LCA considers the environmental impacts of each stage of the value chain of technology (from raw material extraction and manufacturing to operation and

decommissioning). In the search for becoming more robust to inform the energy transition, both ESOM and LCA methodologies have undergone methodological changes.

ESOMs are changing in two ways. First, modelers are extending ESOMs beyond the traditional economic costs (CAPEX, OPEX) and technology coefficients to include other parameters such as land use and material requirements, broadening the scope of optimization. A second line is the development of links with other models in integrated assessment modeling (IAM) suites (see the examples of IMAGE (Stehfest et al., 2014) or MEDEAS (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2020)). Both approaches, though, raise important issues for decision-making, as the epistemology of the models remains unchanged. First, their integration in IAMs has been criticized for being non-transparent (Nikas et al., 2021). Second, the inclusion of parameters beyond techno-economic ones often requires simplifying and harmonizing them into indicators compatible with the assumptions, optimization framework, and internal structures of energy system models, resulting in significant information loss (Henke et al., 2024). Finally, such extensions can create a false sense of robustness, as structural uncertainties in the models remain unaddressed (Puy et al., 2022).

LCA developments on their side are related to changes in the way inventories are calculated and set, as well as how impact methods are defined. Regarding inventories, two major lines of work can be highlighted. First, prospective LCA seeks to change the upstream relations of the value chain of energy technologies to include foreseeable developments of the productive structure (Arvidsson et al., 2018). Second, parameterization of inventories, as well as related software, has come to fill the gap of data for emergent technologies, usually protected due to industrial competition (see, for example, (Sacchi et al., (2019))), or the gap in the background information related to the expected socio-economic changes (see, for example, Douziech et al. (2024)). Methods on their side are evolving towards the inclusion of more environmental impacts under the same cause-effect scheme and the definition of regionalized or temporal characterization factors. Still, LCA epistemology remains constant and is based on linear input-output relations.

Beyond the ESOM-LCA hard links set in integrated assessment suites, the soft, cascaded link of ESOM and impact assessment has generated attention in recent years. These assessments typically perform an LCA (Blanco et al., 2020) or a prospective LCA (Sacchi & Hahn-Menacho, 2024) on an ESOM-calculated technological mix, and the results are later summed up to calculate total impacts. The advantage of the soft link as opposed to the hard link is the possibility of leaving model semantics untouched (keeping the way parameters and relationships are formally represented in the model), thus respecting metrics and minimizing information loss (Weidner et al., 2022). To escape the linearity of LCA in the analysis of impacts in a multilevel contextualized calculation, we developed the ENBIOS framework (Madrid-López et al., 2023) for analyzing the socio-ecological impacts of ESOM configurations. By integrating LCA with socio-ecological metabolism (the study of material and energy flows between societies and ecosystems), ENBIOS enables the calculation of environmental option spaces (de Tomás Pascual et al., 2025) when linked with Calliope models (Lombardi et al., 2020).

2.2 THE NEED FOR MIXED METHODS AND INTEGRATION

Even when quantitative tools are designed to respect semantic coherence and reflect the complexity of the real world, a key challenge remains in integrating qualitative information into these models. This becomes particularly relevant when issues such as justice or social acceptance shape the very definition of the model's 'purpose' and must therefore be explicitly considered in the assessment.

One of the key challenges in achieving methodological integration lies in the disciplinary divide between STEAM and the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). While sustainability is often addressed through energy and environmental modeling rooted in STEAM disciplines, issues such as justice and social acceptance are typically explored through qualitative approaches more common in SSH. This separation limits the potential for holistic assessments. Even when efforts are made to integrate justice into energy modeling (Brückmann et al., 2023), it remains rare to find examples where justice considerations are meaningfully embedded within environmental modeling frameworks. The typical approach here is to combine quantitative and qualitative methods within a mixed methods framework.

Mixed methods, defined as the integration of quantitative and qualitative approaches in research design, have gained traction as a way to produce more robust assessments of complex, “wicked” problems (Mertens, 2015). However, the degree of integration can vary widely, ranging from loosely connected approaches to fully synergistic ones. In connected designs, qualitative and quantitative components are linked but analyzed separately, often with one informing the other or serving as a basis for post-analysis comparison. In contrast, true methodological integration involves continuous interaction between both components throughout the research process. This deeper form of integration allows for the reconfiguration of understanding as different elements are combined, ensuring that methods complement each other and form a cohesive analytical framework (Bazeley, 2024).

The need to integrate mixed methods in the pursuit of a sustainable and just energy transition is widely acknowledged (Brückmann et al., 2023; Sovacool et al., 2015). However, achieving meaningful integration remains challenging for several reasons (Bazeley, 2024; Salgado Junior et al., 2024). First, quantitative methods continue to be privileged over qualitative ones, particularly in energy transition studies where the design of prospective pathways often relies on numerical modeling of technology shares. Second, the sequential structure of many research projects—driven by funding requirements for linear progress—limits opportunities for iterative interaction between methods. Third, there is a general lack of expertise and guidance on designing and implementing truly integrated mixed-methods approaches.

Integrating multiple methodologies requires not only technical knowledge but also a willingness to transform both conceptual frameworks and methodological practices. This transformation is far from straightforward, as the assumptions embedded in modeling approaches are often contested and reflect underlying value systems. As such, model conceptualizations are inherently normative or even political (Lele & Norgaard, 2005). Moreover, social scientific methods do not merely describe reality; they actively shape it. They bring forward particular framings, highlight specific concerns, and influence how problems and solutions are understood (West & Schill, 2022).

2.3 QUANTITATIVE STORYTELLING: MIXING METHODS WITH A PURPOSE

Quantitative Storytelling (QST) offers a methodological approach to addressing the challenge of achieving high-level integration in mixed-methods research. It represents a further development of the Story and Simulation (SAS) approach, in which the narratives or social concerns are iteratively built into scenario storylines and tested through simulation, ensuring that models informing policy are directly relevant to the context and priorities (Alcamo, 2008). However, QST explicitly acknowledges the existence of multiple, often conflicting, policy framings—including economic, ecological, and justice perspectives—and uses quantitative evidence to highlight the trade-offs,

uncertainties, and value judgments behind them (Di Felice et al., 2021; Saltelli et al., 2020). In doing so, it provides a basis for defining and re-evaluating purposes and a model's 'fit-for-purposeness'.

Figure 1 shows the QST cycle used for informed deliberation in narrative assessment. The process begins with a policy narrative or social vision (A), which in our case represents a preferred energy future based on specific beliefs. This narrative is then examined through stakeholder engagement and validation (B), where these beliefs and concerns are identified and incorporated into the quantitative modeling approach by selecting appropriate goals, data, and methods to conduct a holistic assessment (C). The results of this assessment are then synthesized into a useful visualization (D), which helps clarify the trade-offs, synergies, and potential conflicts embedded in the scenario. These insights are brought into a deliberative process (E), where an extended peer community evaluates the scenario. If the scenario is deemed robust and aligned with stakeholder values, the narrative is accepted, which leads to a policy decision (F). If not, the narrative is rejected, and the process loops back to A, initiating a new cycle of co-creation.

Figure 1. The QST methodological cycle

2.4 WORKFLOW

In JUSTWIND4ALL, we carried out two QST cycles, each with distinct goals and iterative feedback loops between modeling, deliberation, and narrative development. The workflow, illustrated in Figure 2, reflects how these cycles are distributed across tasks, case studies, and stakeholder engagements

The **first QST cycle** started with identifying key modeling needs and narrative gaps, as described in the call for proposals (Narratives #1). These covered issues such as the connection between local and global impacts, the balance between onshore and offshore wind, environmental trade-offs, and the overall environmental feasibility of wind energy deployment throughout its lifecycle. These themes guided the initial modeling efforts (Modeling #1), which centered on two case studies: Spain and Portugal. This modeling phase resulted in the creation of new protocols for ENBIOS (e.g., onsite/offsite distribution and improvements to the WindTrace End-of-Life module).

Figure 2. Workflow for this deliverable

The preliminary results were later shared in deliberative spaces (Deliberation #1) of the WindForum (WP4). In WindLab #5 - COMPASS, we engaged with stakeholders and researchers in a workshop in Pineda de Mar held in collaboration with the MarineWind project (not included in the figure, as it was presented in Deliverable 1.2). Meanwhile, under the umbrella of WindLab #2 – Repowering, we completed a round of contact with Portuguese company FINERGE, with whom we collaborated to assess repowering using data from a specific park. Insights from WindLab #1 (Bulgaria) also contributed to this phase; however, only one round was completed for Bulgaria due to some events of this lab being canceled as a result of social protests. These discussions helped reframe the narratives into broader policy challenges (Narratives #2), such as the importance of geographical distribution, the emerging issue of wind turbine end-of-life, and the challenge of widespread public opposition.

The **second QST cycle** built on these revised narratives and focused on refining the modeling tools and outputs (Modeling #2). This included updated assessments for Spain and Portugal, and the first modeling round of the Bulgarian case study. The results were again brought into deliberative settings (Deliberation #2), including:

- Spain: Workshop 3 on results and visualizations for the COMPASS tool in May 2025 in Madrid with representatives from the Spanish Wind Association and the Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITECO), among others.
- Portugal: An interview with representatives from FINERGE (the company operating the wind farm in the case study and having the final say on the end-of-life strategy) following the review of a manuscript with final results (August 2025).
- Bulgaria: Presentation of results in Bulgaria’s Energy Academy hosted by WindLab #1. (To be held in September 2025).

The final outputs of this iterative process include a set of lessons learned—covering both case study-related lessons and overall lessons from the mixed-methods plus fit-for-purpose approach. In the remainder of this deliverable, we present the approaches, methods, results, and lessons learned from the work for each of the case studies. We then move to a section on overall lessons learned from the Work Package.

3 THE BARRIER OF DISTRIBUTED IMPACTS: REGIONALIZATION AND JUSTICE IN SPAIN

3.1 INTRODUCTION: THE CHALLENGE OF SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF BENEFITS AND BURDENS IN THE SPANISH ENERGY TRANSITION

3.1.1 DISTRIBUTIONAL AND COSMOPOLITAN JUSTICE IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

The global energy transition seeks to replace fossil fuel-based energy with renewable energy. While this shift promises significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, it also introduces new environmental and socio-economic challenges. Unlike fossil-based energy systems, where emissions of pollutants are concentrated at the site of power generation, renewable technologies emit much lower amounts but redistribute the environmental burdens along the value chain (Owusu & Asumadu-Sarkodie, 2016). These technologies rely on raw material extraction, processing, and infrastructure manufacturing, activities that are often geographically dispersed and far from the points of energy consumption. Moreover, renewable energy resources such as wind and solar are not evenly distributed across regions, resulting in local spatial imbalances in energy production and resource exploitation (Li et al., 2024).

This reconfiguration of environmental impacts leads to a paradox: while decarbonization efforts may reduce emissions and other impacts locally during energy production, they simultaneously increase pressures on mining and manufacturing sites globally. Communities in resource-rich regions often bear the burdens of these impacts, facing ecological degradation, water scarcity, and social disruption. As a result, renewable energy deployment not only reshapes energy landscapes but also raises critical questions about distributional justice (i.e., how environmental benefits and burdens are allocated across geographies and communities) (Jenkins et al., 2016) and cosmopolitan justice (i.e., all energy justice principles must apply universally to all human beings in all nations) (McCauley et al., 2019).

These considerations highlight the need to examine the energy transition not just through the lens of carbon reduction but also through its broader socio-environmental implications along global supply chains. However, conventional energy planning and sustainability assessments often neglect the quantitative evaluation of distributional and cosmopolitan justice, even though spatial differentiation has been identified as a major challenge in the environmental assessment of energy systems (Blanco et al., 2020).

A thorough analysis of the geographical distribution of the benefits and burdens of the energy transition can contribute to understanding challenges to social acceptance of renewable energy technologies. As outlined above, the transition offers opportunities to deliver tangible local benefits, particularly in communities near fossil fuel power plants scheduled for closure. At the same time, this type of analysis can inform policymakers about the environmental burdens that are outsourced along global supply chains. By making these hidden impacts visible, decision-makers can work toward more equitable trade agreements for materials and primary energy sources, ensuring a fairer and more just transition.

To exemplify this approach, in this case study, we will analyze Spain's planned energy transition by focusing on the electricity system through the lens of distributional and cosmopolitan energy justice. For this purpose, we updated the holistic assessment tool ENBIOS to enable onsite/offsite impact analysis, introducing a novel perspective for assessing spatial trade-offs in impact assessments.

3.1.2 THE ENERGY TRANSITION IN SPAIN

3.1.2.1 Energy system

Any energy system comprises the infrastructure, technologies, and resources involved in producing, converting, and delivering energy, from primary sources (e.g., natural gas) to demand sites (e.g., a gas stove). In Spain, the structure of energy demand by primary energy source has remained relatively stable over the past decade. In 2022, oil products accounted for 52.0% of the total, followed by electricity at 23.8%, natural gas at 15.4%, other renewables and residues (e.g., biomass for heating) at 7%, and coal at 1.5%, a distribution that has seen little variation in recent years (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Structure of the energy demand in Spain in 2012 and 2022 by energy source (shares after conversion to ktep). Non-energy uses are excluded. Own elaboration with data from the (MITECO, 2023; p.24, Table 1.9).

The Spanish National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) sets the objective of increasing the share of renewables in final energy demand to 48% by 2030 (MITECO, 2024; p.23). This ambition builds on the electrification of demand, with electricity projected to cover 35% of final demand in 2030 (MITECO, 2024; p.25), up from 23.8% in 2022, alongside an increase in the renewable share of electricity generation from 56.8% in 2024 (APPA, 2025; p.8) to 81% in 2030 (MITECO, 2024; p.20). Additional measures include enhancing energy efficiency and fostering self-consumption, particularly through rooftop and industrial solar photovoltaics (MITECO, 2024; p.25). Reaching these targets is expected to advance decarbonization while also improving energy security by reducing Spain’s reliance on imported fossil fuels, notably gas from Algeria, the US, and Russia, and oil from the US and Mexico (MITECO, 2024a).

3.1.2.2 Electricity system

Given the central role of the electricity system in Spain’s PNIEC, it is essential to understand its current dynamics. In 2024, wind power emerged as the largest source of electricity, providing 23.2% of the generation mix, ahead of nuclear (20.3%), solar photovoltaics (17.0%), combined cycle gas (13.6%), and hydropower (13.3%). Seasonal patterns are clearly visible: wind power peaks in winter and declines in summer, while solar follows the opposite cycle, helping to balance overall supply. The expansion of renewables has been particularly striking; photovoltaic capacity nearly tripled between 2020 and 2024, rising from 11.74 GW to 31.96 GW (APPA, 2025; p.9). Yet, electricity demand has remained largely stagnant, fluctuating between 251.7 TWh and 256.3 TWh during the

same period (APPA, 2025; p.22). This slowdown mirrors longer-term trends, with both electricity and natural gas consumption in the industrial sector gradually declining since 2000 (IEA, 2025). At the same time, Spain has strengthened its role as a net exporter of electricity, with interconnections to France, Andorra, Portugal, and Morocco enabling exports of 40 TWh in 2024, consolidating a shift that began in 2022.

Building on this current landscape, the PNIEC outlines an ambitious roadmap for the electricity sector. Wind capacity, at around 32 GW in 2024, is planned to almost double to 62 GW by 2030 (MITECO, 2024; p.511). The targets for solar photovoltaics are even more striking: capacity is expected to rise from 32 GW to 76 GW, including 19 GW dedicated to self-consumption (MITECO, 2024; p.25). In terms of generation, wind and solar are projected to deliver 130.1 TWh and 138.3 TWh, respectively, contributing to the plan's goal of 81% renewable electricity by 2030 (MITECO, 2024a).

Other relevant milestones include the complete coal phase-out by 2025 and a progressive nuclear shutdown between 2027 and 2035 (MITECO, 2024a). The latter poses a significant challenge, as nuclear power currently provides about 20% of Spain's electricity demand while ensuring grid stability. To balance this transition, the PNIEC highlights the expansion of storage capacity to 22.5 GW, a key element for integrating variable renewables at scale.

3.1.2.3 Wind energy

Wind energy is central to Spain's electricity transition, both for its historical role and its future targets. Spain was an early mover in the sector, following Denmark's lead with its first commercial wind farms in the 1990s. This early adoption fostered a strong domestic industry, with companies such as Gamesa (now Siemens Gamesa) becoming major European manufacturers. As a result, Spain today has the oldest wind fleet in Europe, with an average turbine age of 14.2 years and more than 60% of turbines older than 15 years (WindEurope, 2025; p.32).

By 2024, Spain ranked as the third-largest European country in installed wind capacity, with 31 GW, equivalent to 11% of the continent's total (WindEurope, 2025; p.30). The fleet consisted of 22,486 turbines across 1,416 wind farms (Budia et al., 2025), concentrated mainly in Castilla y León, Aragón, Castilla La Mancha, and Galicia, regions that are generally less densely populated.

Recent expansion has slowed compared to European leaders: in 2024 Spain added 1.2 GW of new capacity, ranking sixth in Europe, while Germany installed 4.0 GW (WindEurope, 2025; p.14). Although the average size of newly installed turbines reached 5.2 MW, national capacity factors have remained stagnant between 22.5% and 21.5% during 2020–2024 (APPA, 2025; p.10). This reflects the weight of the older fleet, which dilutes the performance gains from new, larger turbines.

While Spain has developed a solid offshore wind industry, the deployment of projects has been slow compared to other European countries. The UK, for instance, already operates 16 GW offshore, whereas Spain currently has only two test sites: PLOCAN in the Canary Islands (research) and DemoSATH in the Basque Country (industrial). A third, PLEMCAT, is expected to open on the Catalan coast in 2025, with three 15 MW connection points. National plans aim for 3 GW of offshore capacity by 2030 (MITECO, 2024a), supported by recently designated maritime zones (MITECO, 2024b). Industry roadmaps, such as the White Book for Offshore Wind (AEE, 2022), envision up to 17 GW by 2050. However, the absence of announced auctions raises questions about the feasibility of meeting the 2030 target, especially as Europe collectively aims for 60 GW offshore by 2030 and 300 GW by 2050.

For onshore expansion, the government has also designated priority deployment areas with different ecological sensitivities (MITECO, 2020), signaling the growing need to balance rapid deployment with environmental protection.

3.2 METHODS

As outlined in Section 2.4, this case study applies the QST approach. This section details the methods used for the modeling steps of the cycle. The results were discussed at a workshop in Madrid in May 2015.

In this work, we assess the spatial distribution of the environmental impacts and benefits of Spain's electricity system transition using ENBIOS. The goal is to explore the environmental trade-offs of Spain's electricity system, comparing the current system (2024) to the PNIEC for 2030, as well as investigating the geographical distribution of environmental burdens and benefits.

Figure 4 depicts the workflow we have followed to carry out this analysis. ENBIOS is the central piece in the workflow, and it is the tool we use to calculate the geographically distributed socio-environmental impacts. To function, ENBIOS requires:

- i. Energy system data coming from either a national plan or from an energy system optimization model. In our case, we take data for 2024 from the Spanish Grid Operator (REE) to evaluate the current situation of the system, and data for 2030 from the Spanish PNIEC to evaluate the future energy system envisioned by the Spanish Government.
- ii. A set of life-cycle inventories that matches the scenario described by the energy system data. In our analysis, we developed a method to disaggregate electricity production inventories into three categories:
 - a) Operational onsite (direct) resource flows (biosphere exchanges).
 - b) Operational offsite (indirect) resource flows embedded in upstream activities (technosphere exchanges).
 - c) Technology infrastructure inventories containing all the flows necessary to build and install the energy infrastructure.

We applied our disaggregation method to life cycle inventories from *Ecoinvent v3.9.1, premise*, and *WindTrace*, a life-cycle inventory parametric model developed within the project and presented in D1.1.

- iii. A set of metrics and a hierarchical dendrogram for analysis. In our analysis, we used the Life Cycle Impact assessment method *Environmental Footprint (EF v3.1)*, covering seven impact categories: climate change, marine eutrophication, ionising radiation, material resource use, energy resource use, water use, and land use. In order to align the metrics to the metrics library presented in D1.2, we applied them to a hierarchical dendrogram, which sheds the focus of analysis into the geographical distribution of benefits and burdens (onsite/offsite). We consider onsite impacts those that happen at the site of electricity production. Conversely, offsite impacts are those that occur elsewhere in the value chain. As proposed in D1.2, we calculate extensive (total electricity system) and intensive (per kWh of electricity produced) impacts.

Figure 4. Workflow applied in this case study. In dark blue, software developed or adapted within the project JW4A (WP1). In pink, input data for ENBIOS. In orange, the electricity system data used for this case study. In pale blue, output of ENBIOS.

Finally, as part of the Deliberation processes of the QST cycle, we held a workshop in Madrid with wind energy policymakers and energy system modelers to discuss the findings of the case study and fine-tune them to improve their usefulness for policymaking. The results presented in the coming sections correspond to those obtained after these discussions.

3.3 RESULTS

3.3.1 VALIDATION OF THE METHOD

The Spanish Grid Operator (REE) releases yearly data on the onsite operational climate change impacts of the Spanish electricity grid, both extensive (total system) and intensive (per kWh). As for our analysis, we took 2024 data on the Spanish electricity system precisely from the Spanish Grid Operator, and we decided to compare our onsite climate change impact results to the ones reported by REE.

We report an extensive onsite climate change impact of 2.53×10^{10} kg CO_{2eq} (Figure 5, left), and an intensive onsite climate change impact of 0.0915 kg CO_{2eq}/kWh. This is consistent with REE data, reporting 2.70×10^{10} kg CO_{2eq} and 0.10 kg CO_{2eq}/kWh. This alignment in our results compared to REE's serves us as a validation of our method.

Figure 5. Extensive (left) and intensive (right) climate change impacts of the Spanish electricity mix operation in 2024.

3.3.2 OPERATION (NATIONAL LEVEL [NUTS0])

3.3.2.1 Total impacts

In this section, we present the environmental trade-offs of operating the electricity system for one year in 2030 compared to its operation in 2024. The results presented here include the total impacts of the system (both onsite and offsite). As shown in Figure 6, almost all analyzed intensive (per kWh) impacts improve in 2030 compared to 2024. The reductions are all around 50%, marine eutrophication being the smallest (46.4%) and ionising radiation the biggest (59.6%). This is the result of PNIEC planning to phase out coal, as well as drastically reducing most other fossil fuel technologies (not gas) by 2030, reducing the direct emission of greenhouse gases, as well as other gases and chemical compounds into the atmosphere and water bodies. Moreover, the reduction of fossil fuels in the system also minimizes the water used for the refrigeration of combustion power plants also leading to a reduction in water use.

However, not all impacts improve by 2030, as land use impacts per kWh are increased by 61.8%. This is mainly due to the larger incorporation of electricity from biomass in PNIEC’s plan compared to 2024. Although biomass plays a modest role in the 2030 scenario (2% of the electricity mix), it involves the management of forest areas, which translates into this land use impact increasing. It is important to stress that, in the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method, the land use indicator does not measure land in terms of surface area (e.g., m²) but rather reflects how land occupation and transformation affect soil quality over time. This impact is expressed in Points (Pt), representing a weighted, normalized assessment of damage to soil functions. As such, it is an indirect measure of land use intensity, capturing qualitative degradation rather than just physical land coverage.

An analysis of the extensive environmental trade-offs between 2030 and 2024 reveals that the reduction of impacts (except land use) is more modest than for the intensive results (Figure 6). This is because PNIEC assumes a 48.4% increase in electricity production (from 262 TWh to 398 TWh), due to the electrification of the economy. Therefore, although Spain would be producing electricity with a cleaner electricity mix, the fact that Spain will be producing 48.4% more electricity than in 2024 makes the extensive impact improvements smaller. For the same reason, the opposite happens with land use, which increases in 2030 with respect to 2024.

Figure 6. Intensive (per kWh) environmental impacts difference (in %) between operating the electricity system in 2030 and 2024.

Figure 7. Extensive environmental impacts difference (in %) between operating the electricity system in 2030 and 2024.

3.3.2.2 Geographical distribution of impacts

During the operation of the electricity system, some emissions (e.g., CO₂) occur directly at the site of the power plant. We refer to these as onsite emissions. These have direct impacts on the local environment and nearby communities, although they can also contribute to global environmental issues. In contrast, other impacts are embedded in the supply chain of auxiliary materials (e.g., ammonia or limestone for an oil power plant) and primary energy sources (e.g., fuel oil). These impacts occur throughout the value chain (during extraction, processing, or manufacturing) and are

often geographically dispersed. Although occasionally such impacts may occur close to the power plant (e.g., biomass growing next to a biomass power plant), we still categorize them as offsite, since systematically tracing the origin of primary energy sources or auxiliary materials on a plant-by-plant basis falls beyond the scope of our method.

The distinction of these onsite and offsite impacts can feed into the distributional justice perspective, as it can highlight where the impacts and benefits of the energy transition are distributed. This subsection presents the geographical distribution of the environmental impacts associated with operating Spain’s electricity system for one year, distinguishing between onsite and offsite impacts, for the years 2024 and 2030.

Figure 8. Intensive (per kWh) onsite environmental impacts difference (in %) between operating the electricity system in 2030 and 2024.

We can see that for all impact categories, the 2030 scenario improves onsite impacts with respect to 2024 (Figure 7). For material resources, energy resources, and land use impacts, the reductions are close to 100%. It is important to highlight, though, that these onsite impacts are very small in absolute terms (see Figure 8), as there is almost no need for onsite land during the operation (the land is necessary during the installation of the power plant), and also very few materials and primary energy sources are required onsite (they are mainly outsourced from somewhere else).

Figure 9. Land use, resource use (minerals and metals) and resource use (fossil) onsite and offsite extensive impacts in 2024 and 2030.

On the other hand, onsite impacts related to water use, ionising radiation, marine eutrophication, and climate change are reduced between 44% (marine eutrophication) and 69.4% (ionising radiation). The reduction in water use is primarily due to a slight decline in electricity generation from hydropower dams. Dams are significant contributors to water depletion, as their large surface areas increase evaporation through exposure to solar radiation (Amrish et al., 2024; Kohli & Frenken, 2015). Since the PNIEC anticipates lower hydropower output, likely due to reduced water availability in reservoirs, this leads to less surface water exposure and, consequently, lower evaporation rates. To a lesser extent, the reduction in water use is also attributed to the decreased reliance on fossil fuel power plants (e.g., nuclear, coal, and gas), which require substantial water for cooling. As the PNIEC plans to phase down these technologies, the associated water losses through evaporation also decline.

The reduction in ionising radiation impacts is primarily driven by Spain’s planned nuclear phase-out, as outlined in the national closure calendar. This includes the scheduled shutdowns of Almaraz (2027–2028), Ascó I (2030), and Cofrentes (2030) in the period 2024-2030. While operational nuclear power plants do emit small amounts of radioactive substances, primarily through cooling water discharges and controlled ventilation, these releases are strictly regulated and kept well within safety limits. Nevertheless, the gradual decommissioning of these facilities significantly reduces the onsite potential for ionising radiation exposure associated with electricity generation.

The reduction in marine eutrophication is largely attributed to the planned phase-out of coal power in Spain, including the closure of the last remaining coal plant in Asturias before 2030. Coal combustion releases significantly higher levels of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) compared to other electricity generation technologies (Saito & Fujiwara, 2023). These NO_x emissions are transported

through the atmosphere and eventually deposited into nearby water bodies, where they contribute to nutrient pollution and trigger marine eutrophication.

Finally, the reduction in climate change impacts is primarily driven by the overall decline in fossil fuel-based electricity generation, especially the phase-out of coal, and, to a lesser extent, the decreased use of natural gas.

Figure 10. Intensive (per kWh) offsite environmental impacts difference (in %) between operating the electricity system in 2030 and 2024.

When comparing the intensity of offsite environmental impacts between 2024 and 2030 (Figure 10), we observe a reduction across all impact categories (except land use), ranging from 41.5% (climate change) to 57.8% (ionising radiation). This trend reflects the conceptual reality that fossil fuel technologies rely more heavily on auxiliary materials and the extraction of primary energy sources (e.g., coal) than renewable technologies (e.g., wind). As such, the overall decline in offsite impacts can largely be attributed to the PNIEC’s strategic shift toward renewable energy.

Looking at individual impact categories, the reduction in material resource use is closely tied to the decreasing need for auxiliary inputs in renewables. For example, coal-fired power plants require materials such as chlorine and fuel oil, and generate various types of ash that must be treated elsewhere. In contrast, wind farms have minimal operational material requirements, typically limited to the replacement of lubricating oil and coolant.

The explanation for the reduction in offsite water use differs. One key assumption of the PNIEC is a significant decline in electricity imports from France by 2030. Since approximately 11% of France’s electricity mix is based on hydropower, primarily from dams, this decrease in imports implies a reduction in water evaporation associated with hydropower generation in France. Consequently, Spain’s offsite water use impact decreases in 2030.

The reduction in energy resources (non-renewable) can be explained by a lower demand for primary energy sources, notably coal and uranium, in 2030.

The land use increase of 61.8% is again explained by the increase in biomass use in 2030. This means higher land extensions, sometimes far away from the electricity production site, are required in this scenario.

Ionising radiation is related to the Spanish nuclear phase-out plan. The closure of several power plants means less uranium requirements for the country, which translates into less exposure to ionising radiation in the mining sites. Marine eutrophication reduction is mainly due to the phase-out of coal. Coal mining releases nitrogen compounds into water bodies. Finally, climate change reduction is also mainly due to coal phase-out, as emissions during the coal mining process are the top contributor to climate change impact in 2024.

3.3.3 OPERATION (REGIONAL LEVEL [NUTS2])

Up to this point, our analysis has focused on the environmental trade-offs of the energy transition at the national level. However, this perspective does not capture the onsite environmental impacts at the regional scale. As discussed in Section 3.1.1, examining these regional/local dynamics can reveal potential benefits for nearby communities, thereby helping to enhance local social acceptance. In this section, we explore how onsite environmental benefits and burdens are distributed across Spain’s NUTS2 regions (Autonomous Communities) under the proposed PNIEC scenario. Since the PNIEC does not specify how future energy technologies will be geographically allocated, we assume that new electricity generation will follow the same regional distribution as in 2024. The 2024 and 2030 electricity mixes for each region are in Annex 9.2.1.

Figure 11 shows the percentage change in regional environmental impact intensity (per kWh) between 2024 and 2030. The results include all impact categories relevant to local ecosystems and human health (namely, marine eutrophication, ionising radiation, and water use) as well as climate change, which is included for reference. It is essential to note that land use impacts are excluded from this analysis, as onsite land use is primarily associated with the installation and physical footprint of the infrastructure, rather than the operation of power plants. These impacts will be addressed in the next section. Green shades indicate regional improvements in onsite environmental impacts, while reddish shades reflect a worsening of impacts.

Figure 11. Percentage change in regional environmental impact intensity (per kWh) between 2024 and 2030

For climate change, there is a general reduction in onsite impacts across all regions. This trend is largely due to the phasing out of fossil fuels and their partial replacement by renewable energy sources. In the case of ionising radiation, reductions are observed only in regions where nuclear power plants are being phased out. These include *Cofrentes* (Comunitat Valenciana), *Almaraz* (Extremadura), and *Ascó I* (Catalunya), all scheduled for closure by 2030. Castilla-La Mancha also shows a decline, as the *Trillo* plant is expected to operate at reduced capacity.

For water use, regional improvements range from 4% in the Basque Country to 56% in Castilla-La Mancha. These reductions are mainly due to a slight decrease in electricity production from hydropower dams, which lowers the extent of water evaporation caused by large exposed water surfaces. On the other hand, marine eutrophication impacts show a mixed pattern, with both improvements and deteriorations depending on the region. Generally, improvements are observed in areas where fossil fuel combustion is reduced, with special mention to coal, such as in Asturias. In contrast, impacts tend to worsen in regions where biomass is expected to play a larger role in electricity generation (like Madrid or Cantabria, see Annex 9.2.1), or where biomass increases mildly in regions where direct emissions from technologies contributing to marine eutrophication are very low in 2024 (see Figure 12) with Extremadura and Castilla y León being the most notable example.

Figure 12. Onsite Eutrophication (marine) impact (per kWh) in the baseline 2024 (top) and PNIEC 2030 scenario (bottom). The maps in Error! No s'ha trobat l'origen de la referència. show the % difference between the two scenarios.

In conclusion, the electricity system transition outlined in the PNIEC generally leads to improvements in onsite environmental impacts across all assessed categories. However, the increased reliance on biomass introduces the risk of increasing marine eutrophication burdens.

3.3.4 INFRASTRUCTURE

In this subsection, we assess the environmental impacts associated with the extraction of raw materials, manufacturing, and installation of the infrastructure required to transition from the current electricity system (2024) to the one proposed in the PNIEC for 2030. These activities occur primarily offsite, outside the regions where the infrastructure is ultimately used, raising important questions about distributional and cosmopolitan energy justice and the outsourcing of environmental burdens. The only partial exception is land use, which is mostly considered an onsite impact, as it directly affects the areas where the infrastructure is installed. However, land is also occupied offsite through mining activities and factory operations involved in material extraction and component manufacturing. Despite these land use impact nuances, in this analysis, we do not divide onsite vs offsite impacts. Given the short timespan between 2024 and 2030, we assume no replacement of existing renewable energy infrastructure due to aging.

The environmental impacts of building the new infrastructure needed for the 2030 electricity system are shown in Table 1. For context, the climate change impact is about 3.74×10^{10} kg CO₂-eq, which equals the emissions from running the current (2024) system for 2.6 years.

We can also look at the breakeven point, the time the 2030 system would need to run compared to the current system, to offset these construction-related emissions (also in Table 1). For climate change, this breakeven point is 9.5 years. After that point, the new system can be considered to have "compensated" for the climate change impacts caused by building the infrastructure. Water use shows a similar breakeven point of around 10 years. In contrast, other impact categories reach breakeven much faster (0.25 years for ionising radiation and 2.58 years for energy resource use).

Table 1. Extensive and intensive (per kW) environmental impacts of building the required infrastructure to go from the 2024 system to 2030.

Impact category	Extensive value	Intensive value (per kW)	Breakeven point (years)
Climate change	9.87E+10 kg CO ₂ -eq	1.27E+03 kg CO ₂ -eq	9.48
Energy resources (non-renewable)	1.19E+12 MJ	1.54E+04 MJ	2.58
Eutrophication, marine	1.50E+8 kg N-eq	1.94 kg N-eq	24.28
Ionising radiation, human health	6.71E+9 kBq U235eq	86.6 kBq U235eq	0.35
Land use	2.40E+10 m ² a	309 m ² a	-
Material resources (minerals and metals)	6.82E+06 kg Sb-eq	0.088 kg Sb-eq	1229.5
Water use	6.05E+10 m ³ world eq	780 m ³ world eq	10

However, not all impacts are offset so easily. For marine eutrophication, the breakeven point rises to over 24 years. Most notably, for material resource use, the breakeven point extends to nearly 1,230 years. This highlights a key challenge of the energy transition: it requires a substantial amount of material extraction, which will never be "compensated for".

While the PNIEC places significant emphasis on expanding storage capacity, both through hydropower storage and chemical batteries, Figure 13 shows that the construction of new power

plants contributes an order of magnitude more to climate change impacts than the addition of new storage infrastructure. Furthermore, the impacts associated with new transmission lines are approximately 200 times lower than those from power plant construction.

Among the technologies, photovoltaics (both open ground and rooftop) are the leading contributors to climate change impacts (Figure 14), followed by onshore wind and solar parabolic technologies. This is explained by looking at PNIEC's targets, which call for a 44 GW increase in photovoltaic capacity, compared to 27 GW for onshore wind and just 3 GW for offshore wind.

Figure 13. Extensive climate change impact of building the required infrastructure to go from 2024 system to 2030, separated into transmission, infrastructure, and storage.

Figure 14. Extensive climate change impact of building the required infrastructure to go from 2024 system to 2030, per technology.

3.4 TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

1. Beyond carbon: Environmental impacts show mostly positive trends, but there are trade-offs

The indicators analyzed suggest that the transition could bring meaningful reductions in several environmental impacts, particularly climate change, ionising radiation, and water use. These improvements are largely linked to the replacement of fossil fuel-based technologies with

renewables. However, not all technologies contribute equally. The increasing role of biomass introduces important challenges, especially in terms of marine eutrophication (due to nitrogen emissions) and land use pressures related to forest resource demand and management. These impacts, while often occurring offsite, must not be overlooked. Focusing exclusively on carbon emissions is insufficient to guide the energy transition. Carbon metrics alone cannot reveal the trade-offs involved in shifting to renewables. Without integrating other environmental and social indicators into assessments, these hidden burdens remain unaddressed. Expanding the scope of analysis is therefore essential to uncover these trade-offs.

2. Spatial perspective can support fairer decision-making

Our analysis of onsite environmental impacts at the regional (NUTS2) level reveals that some communities will benefit more than others, particularly those where fossil fuel infrastructure is phased out. This information can help to enhance local acceptance of renewable projects by making local benefits visible. However, it also reinforces the importance of integrating spatial equity considerations into energy planning, ensuring that regions disproportionately affected by infrastructure development or land use are not left behind.

3. Offsite burdens and global justice concerns

The infrastructure needed to meet 2030 targets comes with significant offsite environmental impacts, from material extraction to water use and land occupation during manufacturing. These burdens are often exported to other regions or countries, raising concerns about distributional energy justice on a global scale. A just transition must recognize these invisible flows of environmental pressure and promote policies that ensure ethical sourcing, resource transparency, and fair international trade frameworks.

4. Breakeven analysis highlights opportunities and bottlenecks

The breakeven point analysis illustrates how long it takes for the operational gains of the future electricity system to offset the upfront environmental impacts of new infrastructure. While some benefits, such as reductions in ionising radiation and energy resource use, are realized almost immediately (within 0.25 and 2.58 years, respectively), other impacts, particularly material resource use, represent a significant bottleneck, with a breakeven point exceeding 1,200 years. From a distributional and cosmopolitan justice perspective, these material-related burdens are often offshored to lower-income countries with less stringent environmental and labor protections, meaning that the environmental benefits of the transition may come at the cost of reinforcing global inequalities.

5. Toward a more just and informed transition

These findings emphasize that while the shift to renewables reduces some impacts, it also reshapes others, across space, time, and communities. A truly sustainable transition requires deliberate planning to avoid shifting burdens elsewhere. Policymakers should embed these insights into national and regional strategies, using them to guide infrastructure siting and supply chain policies. Doing so will help walk towards an energy transition that is not only effective but also fair, balanced, and just.

4 DEALING WITH END-OF-LIFE: ASSESSING STRATEGIES IN A PARK IN PORTUGAL

4.1 INTRODUCTION: THE CHALLENGE OF END-OF-LIFE MANAGEMENT

The expansion of wind power worldwide in the last decades coincides with the need to phase out fossil fuels, creating pressure for both a fast increase in installed power capacity and for managing the stock of aging turbines already in operation. Furthermore, locations with the best conditions for harnessing wind electricity are already occupied by old generation machines, which are now approaching or reaching the end of their technical lifetime. This poses a pressing dilemma regarding the end-of-life management strategy to follow: repowering, modernization, life extension, substitution, or decommissioning. Each strategy has several challenges and advantages. For example, repowering raises productivity at a given site but might deal with limitations such as a lack of a stable regulatory framework, grid capacity, or distance to municipalities (de Simón-Martín et al., 2022; Del Río et al., 2011; Kitzing et al., 2020).

To date, this dilemma has mostly been addressed through techno-economic assessments. Many studies analyze end-of-life strategies at the national or regional level (Grau et al., 2021; Jung et al., 2018; Lacal-Aránegui et al., 2020; Serri et al., 2018; Ziegler et al., 2018), offering valuable insights for energy planning but often relying on generalized assumptions about turbine models or distances to settlements. Such simplifications overlook site-specific factors, such as local wind regimes, which are crucial in practice. Other works examine the issue at the wind farm or turbine level (Colmenar-Santos et al., 2015; de Bona et al., 2021; Nivedh et al., 2013; Rubert et al., 2018; Serri et al., 2018; Villena-Ruiz et al., 2018), but these too remain confined mainly to economic and technical dimensions. As a result, important aspects such as environmental trade-offs or the links between local-scale decisions and system-wide outcomes are often overlooked. This narrow focus risks providing a partial picture of end-of-life strategies, potentially misleading policy or technical choices, and limiting progress toward more sustainable and socially acceptable wind energy transitions.

Only a few studies have assessed environmental impacts, and these remain confined to the scale of the turbine or wind farm. For instance, (Zimmermann & Gößling-Reisemann, 2011) evaluated the carbon footprint and cumulative energy demand of three repowering scenarios for a single turbine in Germany, while (Martínez et al., 2018) analyzed the life cycle impacts of repowering a wind farm in La Rioja (Spain) with a detailed infrastructure inventory but without comparing alternatives. More recently, Kasner (2022) examined decommissioning, repowering, and modernization of a wind farm in Wielkoposka with high material detail, yet still without linking local-scale results to broader system implications. This highlights a clear research gap: integrated assessments are needed that move beyond purely techno-economic perspectives, encompass the full range of end-of-life management options, and combine site-specific detail with system-wide environmental trade-offs. Portugal represents a particularly relevant case study in this context, as it has one of the oldest wind fleets in Europe with an average age of around 14 years, making the end-of-life challenge especially pressing.

To address this gap, in this study we perform a life cycle and social metabolism assessment of a wind park in Portugal (Cabril), testing different end-of-life strategies including life extension, substitution, and repowering. Compared to previous studies, we assess both the utilization factors of materials and the production potential of the location from a metabolic perspective. This holistic approach

captures the specific challenges of modeling end-of-life management of wind parks with LCA, while embedding local-scale results into a broader systems view.

4.2 METHODS

4.2.1 CASE STUDY DESCRIPTION

Our case study focuses on the Cabril wind park in Portugal, whose technical characteristics are provided in Table 2. Cabril, current wind park characteristics and expected repowering scenario.. It was built in two phases: 9 turbines of 1.8 MW in 2002 and 2 turbines of 2 MW in 2005, for a total installed capacity of 20.2 MW. Therefore, at the time of this study, most of the park has reached the end of the typical turbine lifetime (20 years).

*Table 2. Cabril, current wind park characteristics and expected repowering scenario. Data from Wind energy database, *** is paywalled data from the database that can not be openly shared. Data for the Enercon E112/4500 on the rotor diameter and gearbox generator is from (Bauer & Matysik, n.d.). The capacity factor comes from renewables.ninja (Pfenninger & Staffell, n.d.), while the hub height is our own estimation*

Variable	Unit	Cabril I	Cabril II	Cabril	Repowering Common parameters
Wind park power	MW	16.2	4	20.2	22.5
Commissioning year		***	***		2025
Model		Enercon E66/1800	Enercon E70/2000		Enercon E112/4500
Number of turbines		9	2	11	5
Turbine power	MW	1.8	2.0	1.8	4.5
Hub height	m	***	***		120
Rotor diameter	m	66	70		114
Gearbox generator		dd_eesg	dd_eesg		dd_eesg
Initial capacity factor		20.80%	22.30%		29.30%

4.2.2 SCENARIOS

We explored 4 scenarios, represented in Figure 15: (SE) short life extensions (via second-hand material), and (LE) long extension with new parts (modernization), (S) Substitution with the same wind park configuration and (R) repowering of wind turbines. These scenarios differ in which components are substituted, whether replacement parts are new or reused, and whether the turbine is maintained in its original form or repowered. Given current market conditions, some of these configurations **are not realistically feasible**. For example, nowadays, small turbines and their parts are difficult or impossible to find in the market as new. This makes it very difficult to directly replace old turbines with new ones of the same size. However, second-hand markets of used turbines and parts have emerged. This entails an effort to ensure the condition of reused parts. Therefore, substitution and extension scenarios are useful as a reference to show the improvement with respect to the repowered turbine.

Lifetime is a crucial factor in sustainability assessments, yet it remains largely uncertain. Typically, wind turbines are considered to have a 20-year lifespan, though 25 years is fairly common in the industry, and reaching 30 years could also be feasible. However, each component has a different

lifespan. For example, some assessments state that gearboxes are replaced two or three times during a wind turbine's lifetime (Kasner, 2022). Towers and foundations typically last longer. According to Vestas, foundations and cabling may have a lifespan of 50 years (Vestas, 2022, 2023b, 2023a, 2024). Waldron et al., (2018) argue that designing foundations for a 60-year operational lifespan is feasible by using additional materials and assuming that turbines that are geometrically compatible with the connection are available.

This uncertainty in the lifetime of turbines also happens with life extensions. Companies like Siemens consider a life extension of 10 years (Siemens Gamesa, 2022). Greater extensions could be achieved if the nacelle and rotor, which experience the most wear, are replaced. Life extensions of wind turbines can be achieved through the use of second-hand parts. This is often necessary due to the scarcity of new parts on the market, but it requires thorough assessments and regular monitoring of their condition.

Figure 15. End-of-life scenarios of wind turbines. Horizontal arrows define lifetimes, and vertical arrows show main material flows (construction and end-of-life)

4.2.3 WIND PARK MODELING AND LIFE CYCLE INVENTORIES

Foreground inventories were built using *WindTrace* (Sierra-Montoya, 2024), a Python package based on *Brightway2* (Mutel, 2017) developed in T1.1 of WP1. Background data comes from *Ecoinvent v3.9.1* cutoff database (Wernet et al., 2016). *WindTrace* is a parametric model that provides material and other resource requirements for turbines and wind parks, provided a series of input data such as the type of turbine or some manufacturing options.

For this study, we updated *WindTrace* with an end-of-life module that calculates resource requirements for the scenarios explained in the previous section. *WindTrace* provides amounts of materials for a wind turbine or park, but it does not specify how materials are distributed among different parts. In some scenarios, we aim to address the replacement of specific parts (Table 3).

This substitution of different parts was translated into amounts of materials in the updated *WindTrace* module. This was based on data from (Kasner, 2022), which provides the material distribution (in %) for the nacelle, rotor, tower, and foundations. We assume each material distribution in the parts is equal for all turbine types and sizes. For example, 66% of cast iron is in the foundations, and 34% in the rotor. We are only accounting for new inputs. Therefore, the production impacts and materials of reused components are not included. Then, *WindTrace* generates the material inventory for a new turbine and allocates the percentage of the original *WindTrace* inventory's materials that are necessary for replacing specific parts in each scenario.

Table 3. Summary table of description of parts that are necessary for each end-of-life scenario

Scenario	Years	Parts	
		New	Used
Lifetime extension with reused parts	Short lifetime extension (10 years)	Blades	Reused components in the nacelle (second-hand market of decommissioned wind turbines)
Lifetime extension with new parts	Long extension (25 years)	Blades and nacelle (difficult to get from the market)	
Substitution	25 years	Everything but foundations. Foundations would be reused (Toña et al., 2024)	
Repowering	25 years	Everything	

4.2.4 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

We complement the LCA results with a metabolic perspective of the productivity of the Cabril wind park location: we include the lifetime and yearly electricity production and impacts. Yearly electricity production is estimated using a 0.9% attrition rate, reflecting the gradual loss of productivity over the plant's lifetime due to mechanical wear. Consequently, production declines over time (Figure 16; blue, yellow, and black curves).

The LCA functional unit and reference flow in this study is defined as the production of 1 kWh of electricity. We first compare the different end-of-life options (repowering, substitution, short extension, and long extension) on this basis. In a second step, we adopt a system expansion perspective to account for differences in electricity generation across scenarios. By introducing newer and larger turbines, repowering inevitably produces more electricity than substitution or lifetime extension strategies (Figure 16; blue vs orange). To ensure comparability, we assume that the additional electricity generated in the repowering case, but not in the other scenarios, would otherwise be supplied by the Portuguese electricity mix. In this system expansion, the Global Warming Potential (GWP100) impact is calculated as the sum of the scenario-specific results (electricity production) and the emissions from the Portuguese electricity mix supplying the missing electricity. Since it would be unrealistic to assume that the current mix remains constant in the future, we project its gradual decarbonization using the historical trend from 1990 to 2024 (Figure 16; grey and red curves).

Figure 16. Historical and scenario-based electricity production in Cabril wind park

This LCA focuses on impacts still to come, meaning the electricity already generated by the existing wind park is not taken into account. Since end-of-life depends largely on future use, we are allocating to the scenario the end-of-life of the previous configuration (and not the final one of the elements we are installing). End-of-life is not very relevant in terms of LCA impacts (Sierra-Montoya et al., n.d.).

The Life Cycle Impact Assessment method was EF v 3.1, and its following categories/indicators:

- Climate change (global warming potential (GWP100) – kg CO_{2eq}),
- Eutrophication: marine (fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N) - kg N-Eq),
- Water use (user deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption) - m³ world eq. deprived),
- Energy resources: non-renewable (abiotic depletion potential (ADP): fossil fuels - MJ, net calorific value),
- material resources: metals/minerals (abiotic depletion potential (ADP): elements (ultimate reserves) - kg Sb-Eq).

4.3 RESULTS

4.3.1 LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Impacts per kWh vary depending on the impact category and scenario (Figure 17, upper). In general, immediate actions have larger impacts per kWh compared to scenarios that involve lifetime extensions. The Substitution scenario tends to have slightly higher impacts per kWh than

Repowering for climate change (115%), water use (122%), energy resources: non-renewable (113%), and eutrophication: marine (110%). This pattern changes with mineral resources, where repowering scenarios have 132% higher impacts per kWh. Lifetime extensions, especially long-term extensions using new parts, also produce lower impacts per kWh. However, this comes at the cost of generating less electricity. Electricity production is very similar across scenarios with smaller wind turbines.

Figure 17. Impacts per year (upper) and per kWh (lower) of the scenarios in the Cabril wind park

	impacts per year										
	Power capacity	lifetime	yearly electricity production	LCA GHG of wind park + externalised GHG	EF v3.1					LCI	
					climate change	water use	energy resources: non-renewable	eutrophication: marine	material resources: metals/minerals		direct material investments
					ton CO _{2e} /year	1000 m ³ /year	GJ/year	kg/year	kg Sb-Eq/year		ton/year
MW	years	GWh/year	ton CO _{2e} /year	ton CO _{2e} /year	1000 m ³ /year	GJ/year	kg/year	kg Sb-Eq/year	ton/year		
Repowering	22.5	25	51.9	439	439	213	5425	604	17	470	
Substitution	20.2	25	33.6	814	327	168	3956	430	8	111	
Long extension	20.2	25	33.6	1650	163	98	2168	273	6	34	
Short extension	20.2	10	35.9	3214	240	177	3408	279	3	37	
Repowering	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Substitution	90%	100%	65%	413%	75%	79%	73%	71%	49%	24%	
Long extension	90%	100%	65%	376%	37%	46%	40%	45%	36%	7%	
Short extension	90%	40%	69%	733%	55%	83%	63%	46%	19%	8%	

	impacts per electricity production									
	lifetime	yearly electricity production	LCIA climate change + direct externalised electricity mix	EF v3.1					LCI	
				climate change	water use	energy resources: non-renewable	eutrophication: marine	material resources: metals/minerals		direct material investments
				kg CO _{2e} /MWh	m ³ /MWh	MJ/MWh	g N-Eq/MWh	g Sb-Eq/MWh		kg/GWh
years	GWh/year	kg CO _{2e} /MWh	kg CO _{2e} /MWh	m ³ /MWh	MJ/MWh	g N-Eq/MWh	g Sb-Eq/MWh	kg/GWh		
Repowering	25	51.9	8.4	8.4	4.1	104	11.6	0.32	9055	
Substitution	25	33.3	54.5	9.8	5.0	119	12.9	0.24	3327	
Long extension	25	33.3	49.6	4.9	3.0	65	8.2	0.18	1013	
Short extension	10	35.6	90.4	6.7	5.0	96	7.8	0.09	1046	
Repowering	25	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
Substitution	25	64%	645%	116%	123%	114%	111%	76%	37%	
Long extension	25	64%	587%	58%	72%	62%	71%	56%	11%	
Short extension	10	68%	1070%	80%	121%	92%	67%	27%	12%	

This typical LCA view uses a functional unit of 1 kWh of electricity produced. However, looking at the bigger picture, lower impacts per kWh of substitution and longer lifespans often come at the cost of producing less electricity. Efficiency can be analyzed from different angles, not just kgCO_{2e} per kWh, but also which configuration yields more electricity by optimizing location. It is important to consider scale, not just impact indicators per kWh. Given that system lifetimes vary in our scope, we use average yearly production to account for these differences.

In extensive terms, the scenario that generates fewer yearly averaged impacts is long extension substitution. This is because it generates less electricity at low impacts/kWh. In fact, impacts are mostly produced during the infrastructure construction, and so at the beginning of the lifetime.

4.3.2 EXTERNALISED GREENHOUSE GAS (GHG) EMISSIONS

In this kind of assessment of different possible wind park configurations, we not only want to decrease as much as possible the life-cycle impacts per kWh, but also to produce as much electricity as possible in a given location. We have seen that the repowering scenario generates more life-cycle emissions (8.4 g CO_{2e}/kWh) than the lifetime extensions (long: 4.9 and short: 6.7 g CO_{2e}/kWh).

To assess the impacts of the externalized electricity production, we calculate the direct GHG emissions generated by the Portuguese electricity mix to overcome the electricity that could have been generated in that location in the Repowering case (Figure 5). The carbon intensity is extrapolated from the 1990-2022 trend (European Energy Agency, 2024).

The results are shown in Figure 17, lower. In that case, the climate change impacts of scenarios other than repowering increase significantly. Short extension emissions per kWh (90 g CO_{2e}/kWh) are more than ten times higher than those from repowering. Substitution (54 g CO_{2e}/kWh) and Long extension (49 g CO_{2e}/kWh) emissions, which include the carbon footprint of the outsourced electricity mix, are six times larger than repowering. The notable difference in the short extension is due to the assumption that the Portuguese electricity mix will have net-zero direct emissions by 2043. Consequently, long lifetime scenarios involve substantial electricity production supplemented by a nearly carbon-neutral electricity mix, while the short extension's expected lifetime results in emissions around 100 g CO_{2e}/kWh based on the Portuguese electricity mix.

We could also extrapolate the impacts of each scenario per kWh to address how many extensive impacts could we expect. However, we would need an equivalent location to install wind turbines, occupying more space and using more materials. It is possible that the marginal location where to install wind turbines has worse conditions and therefore, even more impacts and materials are required to produce the same electricity.

4.4 TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

1. Repowering increases electricity output at Cabril

The repowering scenario for the Cabril wind park demonstrates a clear advantage in terms of electricity generation. By replacing older turbines with larger, more efficient models, the site's productivity is maximized, making better use of the available wind resource and land. This strategy is particularly relevant given the aging infrastructure and the limited availability of high-quality wind sites in Portugal.

2. Lifetime extensions offer lower impacts per kWh but reduce total energy yield

Extending the life of existing turbines, either through reused or new parts, results in lower environmental impacts per unit of electricity produced. These scenarios make efficient use of existing infrastructure, especially foundations and towers, and reduce the need for new materials. However, they also produce significantly less electricity over time, which may require compensatory installations elsewhere to meet energy targets.

3. Site-specific conditions shape the feasibility of end-of-life strategies

The Cabril case highlights the importance of tailoring end-of-life strategies to the specific characteristics of each wind park. Factors such as turbine age, wear, local wind conditions, and grid capacity influence the viability of repowering versus extending turbine life. Moreover, market availability of parts, especially for older turbine models, can constrain certain options, making second-hand components a practical but uncertain solution.

4. Designing for modularity could unlock future reuse potential

The case study highlights the importance of designing turbines with modularity and durability in mind. Modular design would facilitate future lifetime extensions and reduce the environmental footprint of wind energy systems. In Cabril, the ability to reuse foundations and towers was a key factor in reducing impacts, but broader reuse was limited by the original design of the turbines.

5 FROM POLARIZED OPPOSITION TO INFORMED, DECISION-MAKING: DEALING WITH UNCERTAINTY IN BULGARIA

5.1 INTRODUCTION: UNDERSTANDING THE CHALLENGE OF WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN BULGARIA

In Bulgaria, the development of wind energy, particularly offshore, faces a complex interplay of socio-political, historical, and institutional challenges. The legislative process for offshore wind was frozen in early 2024 after the first reading of the draft Law on Energy from Renewable Sources in Maritime Spaces in Parliament, which was followed by a wave of amendments triggered by protests from the fishing and tourism sectors (Pandev & Medzhedeliieva, 2024). These groups voiced concerns over visual impacts, marine biodiversity, and fish stocks—concerns that were further amplified by disinformation campaigns and sensational claims in the public domain. Examples of such tactics included portraying turbines as lethal to nearby residents, predicting economic collapse, or claiming species loss and environmental catastrophe without evidence (Vladimirov et al., 2025).

At the same time, the potential socio-economic benefits of wind energy—such as port modernization, job creation, and synergies with hydrogen and aquaculture—have been largely absent from the debate. Besides, Bulgaria's energy planning has historically followed a top-down model, shaped by centralized institutions and a legacy of geopolitical alignment with Russia, which continues to influence public perceptions of fossil-based energy sovereignty and externally driven reforms (Vladimirov et al., 2025). The Russian invasion of Ukraine has underscored the strategic vulnerability of fossil fuel dependence, reinforcing the urgency of transitioning toward domestic, clean, and resilient energy sources. The country's entry into the European Union (EU) has started to challenge the model of a centralized energy system dominated by large, state-owned fossil fuel-based companies, and has influenced the public's view about energy transition. Bulgaria's current energy mix remains heavily reliant on imported natural gas, particularly for industrial use and heating. Despite exceptional wind potential, especially in the North-East region (Severoiztochen) and the Black Sea maritime zone (COM/2020/741 Final, 2020), renewable energy deployment has lagged.

The country has experienced three distinct phases in wind energy development: a 'boom' period (2008–2014) driven by EU-aligned incentives and feed-in tariffs; a 'freezing' phase (2015–2020) marked by retroactive policy changes and administrative instability; and a tentative 'revival' phase (2020–present), characterized by market-based project proposals and renewed interest in offshore wind (Uzunov & Trifonova, 2024). Key milestones in this latest phase include the recognition of the Black Sea's potential in the 2020 EU Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy, the launch of the Marine Renewable Energy Academy in Varna, and the formulation of Bulgaria's first offshore wind targets by the Energy Transition Commission in 2022–2023. Nevertheless, these milestones implementation has been repeatedly delayed by political bargaining, lobbying from the tourism and nuclear sectors, and persistent social opposition.

In this context, the mismatch between climate urgency and policy action is increasingly evident. Bulgaria is bound by the European Green Deal and must move toward carbon neutrality by 2050. The country's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP)(Government of Bulgaria, 2025) shows ambition in meeting its renewable energy targets, particularly for offshore wind, and public attitudes toward renewables are generally positive, but perceptions of wind energy vary significantly across municipalities. While some areas—such as Kavarna, Dobrich, and Balchik—

actively support wind projects, others remain influenced by past controversies and protest movements. These divergent views underscore the importance of tailored communication strategies that build trust, clarify benefits, and counter misinformation—especially in the context of offshore wind, where public awareness remains low and support is not yet deeply established.

In this climate of distrust and fragmented narratives, technical evidence alone cannot establish legitimacy (Saltelli & Giampietro, 2017). Modeling results can be misunderstood, challenged, or strategically reframed to support conflicting agendas. In Bulgaria, the accumulation of perceived risks and unassessed opportunities illustrates that while the primary goal of modeling is to provide analytical insights, its limitations in addressing social concerns can indirectly affect acceptance of energy transitions. To support a more robust and socially grounded transition, our approach critically examines the uncertainty inherent in modeling and emphasizes the need for participatory methods. To operationalize this, we conducted a holistic impact assessment using the WindSES library (Madrid López et al., 2025) to compare two scenarios from Bulgaria’s NECP. The assessment focuses on cumulative life cycle indicators, including global warming potential, water use, soil quality, mineral resource scarcity, and marine eutrophication.

5.1.1 BULGARIA’S ENERGY LANDSCAPE & OFFSHORE POTENTIAL

Fossil and nuclear sources still dominate Bulgaria’s current energy mix. Solid fuels account for 44.8% of primary energy production, followed by nuclear energy at 32.6%. Renewable energy sources (RES) account for about 21% of the electricity mix, but wind has a negligible contribution to that. The remaining energy comes from thermal energy (0.5%), natural gas (0.1%), and other sources such as oil and non-renewable waste (0.7%) (see Table 4).

Despite the current absence of offshore wind in Bulgaria’s energy mix, the country holds significant potential in the Black Sea (Trifonova & Vladimirov, 2021), with an Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) wind potential of 116 GW. Of these, 26 GW could be developed using bottom-fixed technologies. The most favorable area for offshore wind development is in the northernmost part of Bulgaria’s EEZ, near the Romanian border. This zone spans approximately 405 km², with wind speeds between 7.6 and 8 m/s at a height of 150 meters and maximum sea depths of 60 meters, thus the bottom fixed potential.

Table 4. Share distribution of the primary energy mix. Current mix against WEM and WAM scenarios (Government of Bulgaria, 2025)

Source / Technology	2005 Share (%)	WEM Share (%)	WAM Share (%)
<i>Solid Fuels (e.g., coal)</i>	44.8	8.49	2.02
<i>Nuclear Energy</i>	32.6	54.34	55.33
<i>Renewable Energy Sources</i>	21.3	—	—
On-shore wind	—	6.63	8.89
Off-shore wind	—	—	3.39
Solar (PV)	—	16.94	18.63
Hydro-pump	—	10.31	9.74
Biomass	—	2.95	1.69
<i>Thermal Energy</i>	0.5	—	—
<i>Natural Gas</i>	0.1	0.21	0.18
<i>Others (e.g., oil, waste)</i>	0.7	—	—
Liquid fuels	—	0.14	0.14

At the EU level, the Black Sea Basin has been designated a priority offshore grid corridor under the TEN-E Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2022/869, 2022), emphasizing its strategic role in Europe’s clean energy future. In this context, Bulgaria and Romania are exploring the development of a joint energy

island in the Black Sea. This initiative aims to support large-scale renewable integration, enhance regional cooperation, and benefit both EU and non-EU countries, including Turkey, Georgia, and Ukraine.

Bulgaria has developed two key energy transition scenarios as part of its National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP): the "With Existing Measures" (WEM) and "With Additional Measures" (WAM) scenarios. These scenarios are aligned with the EU's 'Fit for 55' legislative package, which aims to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. The package also sets targets for renewable energy share (at least 42.5%, aiming for 45%).

- The WEM scenario reflects a continuation of current policies and investment trends, based on fixed macroeconomic projections through 2050. It assumes no major policy shifts beyond those already adopted.
- The WAM scenario, by contrast, outlines a more ambitious pathway aligned with the EU's long-term climate goals. It incorporates expanded and additional measures to accelerate decarbonization and achieve net-zero emissions by 2050.

As Table 4 shows, the WEM scenario maintains a higher share of solid fuels (8.5%) and lower penetration of renewables, with solar PV at 16.9% and onshore wind at 6.6%. However, the reduction of solid fuels and the increase in renewables to around 38% still fall short of the EU's 42.5% renewable energy target. The WAM scenario shows a rise in nuclear energy to 55.3% and in PV and onshore wind to 18.6% and 8.9%, respectively. Offshore wind, which is currently absent from the mix, is introduced with a 3.4% share, reflecting its emerging strategic importance. This scenario aligns more closely with EU goals, reducing solid fuels to 2.02% and increasing renewables to about 42.3%, including offshore wind at 3.39%. However, both scenarios depend heavily on nuclear energy (over 54%). As shown in Figure 18, both scenarios involve a significant shift in the energy mix, reducing reliance on coal while increasing photovoltaics and nuclear power. Wind energy, though increased, remains a secondary element in the country's transition scenarios.

Figure 18. Evolution of the electricity mix in Bulgaria in relation to the WEM and WAM scenarios (Data from IEA and Bulgaria's NECP)

5.2 METHODOLOGY: UNDERSTANDING TRADE-OFFS AND THEIR ASSOCIATED UNCERTAINTY

The objective of this study is to understand the uncertainty associated with the trade-offs of incorporating wind power into the energy mix, with an assessment of cumulative life cycle impacts resulting from each technological choice. To do so, the environmental impacts of the WAM and WEM scenarios from Bulgaria’s NECP 2030 are assessed using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). First, the scope, functional unit, and system boundaries are defined. Once the framework is established, a Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) is developed, collecting all relevant data related to the energy technologies included in each scenario. Following data collection, relevant environmental impact categories are selected. Consequently, the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) is then carried out, translating inventory data into quantified environmental impacts across the selected categories. To account for uncertainties in category impacts, an exploratory sensitivity analysis is performed using Monte Carlo Simulation, which allows for the generation of a probabilistic range of results. Based on this, a more detailed global sensitivity analysis is conducted employing Morris Screening and Sobol indices. For a clear picture of the methodological steps, a diagram is displayed below.

Figure 19. Workflow for the assessment of the uncertainty in the Bulgarian study

5.2.1 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

5.2.1.1 Preanalytical choices

In this LCA we evaluate the trade-offs of the 2030 electricity production scenarios outlined in the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP). The study compares the “With Existing Measures” (WEM) and “With Additional Measures” (WAM) scenarios using a cradle-to-gate LCA approach. This is, it focuses on electricity generation only, excluding transmission, distribution, and end-use sectors due

to data limitations. The functional unit is defined as 1 kilowatt-hour (1 kWh) of electricity produced, allowing for consistent comparison across technologies and scenarios. The system boundaries include all upstream and operational stages of the technologies, from raw material extraction to end-of-life treatment.

We focus only on electricity production technologies due to the lack of disaggregated data for the transport and heating sectors in the NECP scenarios. This is to ensure data availability and methodological robustness.

5.2.1.2 Building the Life Cycle Inventory

We built the LCI using data from the Ecoinvent 3.9.1 cut-off model, which assigns the full environmental burden to the first product life cycle, thereby avoiding double-counting. The inventory encompasses all electricity generation technologies represented in the WEM and WAM scenarios of Bulgaria’s NECP.

To ensure contextual relevance, we tailored the inventories to the Bulgarian context by incorporating region-specific data gathered through a targeted literature review. This review informed the adaptation of key technical parameters, such as capacity, efficiency, and technology type, for each electricity generation technology included in the Bulgarian scenarios, except photovoltaics. In this case, only efficiency was adapted to reflect typical performance of PV modules under Bulgarian solar irradiation conditions. Customized inventories for wind power technologies were developed using WindTrace (Sierra-Montoya et al., 2025) a parametric model designed for high-resolution wind energy assessments. Data sources and the adaptation of inventories can be consulted in Table 5.

Table 5. Inventory data sources

Technology inventory	Data source	Location	Adaptation
Offshore wind 15 MW turbine	WindTrace	BG	Power: 15 MW Floating Platform: Made of steel and semi-submersible Sea Depth: 60 meters Distance from Shore: 28 kilometers (Note: This value is based on the PLEMCA pilot project and extrapolated for the Black Sea depth profile) Approximate Coordinates: (43.19089, 28.27717) Capacity Factor: 40% [Source: https://www.renewables.ninja/] Tower Height: 260 meters Rotor Diameter: 220–240 meters (Estimated based on comparable models such as the Vestas V236-15.0 MW and GE Haliade-X 15 MW) Hub Height: 150 meters (Estimated based on tower height)
Onshore wind 3 MW turbine	Windtrace	BG	Power: 3 MW Foundation: 400 cubic meters of concrete and 40 metric tons of reinforcement Steel (data interpolated from Fântânele-Cogealac Wind Farm from Romania) Coordinates: 43.44152, 28.44300, Kavarna Capacity factor: 34-36% Tower height: 145 m Rotor diameter: 90 m Hub height: 100 m

Technology inventory	Data source	Location	Adaptation
			Type of generator: Asynchronous with converter
Photovoltaic 570 kWp open ground installation, multi-crystalline silicon	Ecoinvent	GLO	Representative Coordinates: 42.192° N, 24.333° E (Plovdiv, Bulgaria) Panel Tilt Angle: 36° facing South [Source: https://profilesolar.com/locations/Bulgaria/Plovdiv/] Annual Irradiation: 1500 kWh/m ² [Source: PVGIS - https://pvgis.com/ca] Panel Type: Bifacial panels (ground installation) Effective Efficiency: 10% in ground installations [Source: https://www.aforenergy.com/bifacial-solar-panels-everything-you-need-to-know/]
Hydropower run-of-river	Ecoinvent	BG	None
Biomass CHP wood chips, 6667 kW	Ecoinvent	BG	None
Nuclear pressurized water reactor	Ecoinvent	BG	None
Natural gas conventional power plant	Ecoinvent	BG	None
Oil electricity production	Ecoinvent	BG	None
Lignite electricity production	Ecoinvent </td <td>BG</td> <td>None</td>	BG	None

5.2.2 METRIC CHOICES

For this assessment, we adapt two metrics from the WindSES library (Madrid-López et al., 2025). For an assessment of the environmental trade-offs, we use the Screening set of metrics (of_X), adapting them to provide results on global impacts. The screening metric builds on established LCA methods to evaluate environmental impacts across multiple levels of analysis (from n-3 to n) as illustrated in Figure 20. Figure 39 in the annex shows the values of the levels and the dendrogram for each one of the scenarios.

Figure 20. Levels connected in the WindSES Offsite Screening (left) and Electricity Community Surplus (right) metric

For the sake of comparing results, we use two LCIA methods: ReCiPe 2016 v1.03 (H) no LT (midpoint and endpoint) (Huijbregts et al., 2017), Environmental Footprint v3.1 no LT (Andreas Bassi et al., 2023) and Cumulative Energy Demand. The selection of methods follows recommendations from the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe. This organization identifies the following key environmental indicators for evaluating electricity generation technologies: climate change, freshwater eutrophication, ionizing radiation, human toxicity (both carcinogenic and non-

carcinogenic), land occupation, water dissipation, resource use (materials and non-renewable energy), and endpoint indicators like damage to ecosystems and human health (UNECE, 2022, p. 48). Table 6 summarizes the definition of the indicators used for the assessment.

Table 6. Indicators and methods used for the calculation of the screening and the surplus metrics

Matric & Method	Impact Indicator	Definition	Unit
(Screening) ReCIpe 2016 v1.03 Midpoint (H)	Climate change	Contribution to global warming from GHG emissions over 100 years	kg CO ₂ -eq
	Freshwater eutrophication	Nutrient enrichment of freshwater systems, mainly due to phosphorus	kg P-eq
	Ionising radiation	Human exposure to ionising radiation compared to Co-60	kg Co-60-eq
	Human toxicity (carcinogenic)	Potential damage to human health from carcinogenic substances	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq
	Human toxicity (non-carcinogenic)	Potential damage from non-carcinogenic toxicants	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq
	Land use	Occupation of land for agriculture and its ecological impact	m ² a crop-Eq
	Resource use: metals/minerals	Depletion of metal and mineral resources	kg Cu-eq
	Resource use: fossil fuels	Depletion of fossil energy carriers	kg oil-eq
	Water use	Amount of freshwater consumed throughout the system	m ³
(Screening) ReCIpe 2016 v1.03 Endpoint (H)	Human health	Damage to human health (e.g., diseases, premature death)	DALYs
	Ecosystem quality	Impact on biodiversity and ecosystems	PDF·m ² ·year
	Natural resources	Future cost or effort for resource extraction	USD 2013
(Screening) EF v3.1 Midpoint	Climate change	Global warming from GHG emissions over 100 years	kg CO ₂ -eq
	Freshwater eutrophication	Nutrient emissions (mainly phosphorus) reaching freshwater compartments	kg P-eq
	Ionizing radiation (human health)	Human exposure to ionizing radiation relative to U-235	kBq U-235-eq
	Human toxicity (carcinogenic)	Toxic effects on humans caused by carcinogenic substances	CTUh
	Human toxicity (non-carcinogenic)	Toxic effects on humans from non-carcinogenic substances	CTUh
	Land use	Soil quality loss due to land transformation or occupation	Index (dimensionless)
	Resource use: metals/minerals	Abiotic depletion based on ultimate reserves	kg Sb-eq
	Water use	Water scarcity measured by user deprivation potential	m ³ world eq. deprived
	Particulate matter formation	Human health impacts from inhalable particles	Cases/year·Disease incidence
(Surplus) Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	Non-renewable energy resources	Energy from fossil sources (coal, oil, gas, nuclear)	MJ·Eq
	Renewable energy resources	Total energy from renewable sources (biomass, wind, solar, hydro)	MJ·Eq
	Renewable biomass	Energy derived from renewable biomass resources	MJ·Eq
	Renewable solar	Energy collected from solar radiation	MJ·Eq
	Renewable water	Energy from hydro sources	MJ·Eq
	Renewable wind	Energy from wind turbines	MJ·Eq

While midpoint methods offer 'objective' indicators, the endpoint approaches aggregate impacts into damages affecting three protection areas: Human Health, Ecosystem Quality, and Resource Availability. The Environmental footprint method indicators are included because it is the LCIA method recommended by the European Commission under the Product Environmental Footprint initiative. This method features midpoint indicators adapted to European environmental conditions, with updated characterization factors for categories like water use, particulate matter, and land use. EF v3.1 aligns with EU policy frameworks and datasets to ensure consistency.

The surplus indicators are also calculated with an LCA perspective using the Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) method (Frischknecht et al., 2015). The CED method returns information about the total use of energy needed to produce and operate the technology required in each scenario and it is an indicator of how efficient the system is. It quantifies the total primary energy requirement (renewable and non-renewable) throughout the life cycle of a system. It includes all energy inputs, direct and indirect, expressed in terms of Higher Heating Value (HHV). CED serves as a screening indicator and a basis for evaluating energy efficiency.

5.2.3 UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

In a context marked by low public trust and widespread misinformation, such as the current debate around wind energy in Bulgaria, the robustness of environmental assessments becomes especially critical. However, this robustness is difficult to ground in evidence when the analytical methods themselves carry high levels of uncertainty. Although academic and institutional bodies widely recommend LCA indicators, they are not without limitations. LCA results are influenced by multiple sources of uncertainty, including assumptions about technological parameters (e.g., efficiency, lifetime), generalized technology profiles, and the projected composition of future electricity systems. This inherent uncertainty in LCA calculations can lead to divergent results and interpretations (Igos et al., 2019).

A central goal of this study is to address these uncertainties, as they are especially important when comparing policy scenarios. We complement this with a comprehensive analysis of how sensitive each indicator is to changes in scenario and technology. First, we conduct an exploratory Monte Carlo analysis, followed by a global sensitivity analysis using Sobol indices, to identify which technologies within the electricity mix make the most significant contribution to environmental impacts.

5.2.3.1 Sensitivity exploratory analysis (Monte Carlo)

To handle the uncertainty in life cycle inventory data and the limitations of deterministic LCIA results, we conducted a sensitivity analysis with Monte Carlo simulation, a popular exploratory method in LCA. All these uncertainties come together in the activities associated with the technologies defined in the inventories.

The Monte Carlo method involves repeatedly sampling input parameters from their respective probability distributions for each inventory and activity, allowing uncertainty to be propagated through the model. As a result, it produces a range of possible outcomes, facilitating a more robust interpretation and comparison of environmental impacts across different scenarios. In most cases, the Bulgarian inventories are represented by a lognormal distribution, as the majority of activities within each technology are recognized to follow this pattern. However, in a few cases, the normal distribution is applied to specific activities.

To assess the sensitivity of the environmental impacts of the WEM and WAM electricity mixes, we conducted 500 Monte Carlo iterations per scenario. This sample size strikes a balance between

computational efficiency and statistical reliability, as per the Central Limit Theorem. According to the Central Limit Theorem (CLT), even when the underlying data distribution is unknown or non-normal, the distribution of sample means tends toward normality as the sample size increases, provided the sampling is consistent and independent. This supports the use of Monte Carlo simulations for estimating central tendencies, particularly when input uncertainties are derived from expert judgment or pedigree scoring, as in the Ecoinvent database. Simulation studies have shown that sample sizes as low as 30 can be sufficient for the CLT to apply, with larger sample sizes such as 500 offering improved stability and convergence (Okoro, Awodiran, & Ayinde, 2023). While 500 iterations may not ensure full convergence of all distribution properties, they are generally adequate for estimating central tendencies in exploratory sensitivity analyses. It should be noted, however, that the distribution of simulated outputs reflects input variability and should not be mistaken for the sampling distribution of the value itself.

5.2.3.2 Global sensitivity analysis (Sobol indices)

While traditional LCA and Monte Carlo simulations provide valuable estimates of environmental impacts and associated uncertainties, they are limited in their ability to identify which specific technologies contribute most to overall variability (Saltelli et al., 2008). In the context of energy transition planning, this level of detail is essential, not only for comparing scenarios but to understand which technologies are driving impacts. Such insights are crucial for informing the definition of key targets, including mitigation strategies and investment priorities.

To address this need, this study applies the Sobol indices to extend beyond average impact estimates by quantifying the effects of changes in individual technological inputs on environmental outcomes.

This method provides a quantitative decomposition of output variance. It estimates first-order indices (individual effects), second-order indices (pairwise interactions), and total-order indices (combined effects including all interactions). Implemented here using a quasi-random sampling strategy with 512 base samples, the Sobol analysis provides a detailed and robust understanding of how each technology contributes to impact variability (Saltelli et al., 2010; Sobol, 2001). Previous studies have shown that 512 or 1024 base samples are generally sufficient to obtain reliable estimates of first- and second-order indices in models with a moderate number of inputs (Saltelli et al., 2010; Pianosi et al., 2016). Therefore, this sample size provides a balance between computational efficiency and the accuracy of sensitivity order estimates.

5.3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

5.3.1 TRADE-OFFS OF FUTURE ENERGY SCENARIOS

5.3.1.1 Screening metrics

The LCIA results presented in the figures below, such as the normalized ReCiPe Midpoint (H) scores across different impact categories, offer a comparative view of the environmental performance of the WEM and WAM electricity mixes.

The LCA comparison of the WEM (With Existing Measures) and WAM (With Additional Measures) scenarios for Bulgaria's energy systems reveals distinct environmental trade-offs that are dependent on the method (Figure 21). Based on maximum-normalized ReCiPe Midpoint impact scores, the WEM scenario typically shows higher environmental burdens across most categories, including water use, land occupation, freshwater eutrophication, both carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic human

toxicity, fossil fuel consumption, and global warming. Conversely, the WAM scenario, which incorporates additional mitigation measures, performs better in these areas but results in higher impacts related to mineral resource scarcity and ionizing radiation. These findings underscore the need for further infrastructure development in the WAM scenario and highlight the significant role of nuclear power in the energy mix. However, the difference is minor, as both scenarios have similar nuclear shares. Overall, these results suggest that while WAM is generally more sustainable, careful consideration of its material demands is essential.

Figure 21. Midpoint results normalized by maximum for methods ReCiPe (left) and EF (right).

A comparison of the ReCiPe (left) and EF 3.1 (right) Midpoint methods highlights two key differences. The results for ionizing radiation are similar with both methods, with the WAM scenario. Concerning mineral resource scarcity, the EF method, compared to the ReCiPe method, shows increasing impacts in the WEM scenario, although the difference between scenarios remains modest with this approach. The difference highlights the importance of the choice of method.

Figure 22. Endpoint impacts to ecosystems, humans and resource areas

The comparison between the midpoint and endpoint results of the ReCiPe method offers complementary insights into the environmental impact of the WEM and WAM scenarios. Midpoint indicators (Figure 21) reflect impacts at an earlier stage in the cause-effect chain, while endpoint indicators (Figure 22) combine midpoint results to illustrate the overall effects on humans, ecosystems, and resource depletion. The figures show that the WEM scenario has a significantly greater impact on humans and ecosystems. However, regarding resource demands, both scenarios appear similar, although the WEM scenario still has slightly higher impacts.

However, relying solely on these deterministic LCIA values does not account for the underlying uncertainty in input data or model assumptions, and ignoring this can lead to misguided policy decisions. Without considering variability and potential overlap in impact outcomes, the observed differences may be misleading or not statistically significant. For a more robust interpretation and to provide better insights about the uncertainty of these results, we next comment on the results of a Monte Carlo simulation.

5.3.1.2 Surplus metric: cumulative energy demands

The CED indicator measures the total primary energy required across all life cycle stages of a technology, from raw material extraction to manufacturing, installation, operation, and end-of-life, categorized. In this case, it means the energy demand of the electricity production sector. This demand is influenced by Bulgaria’s energy mix and economic structure, as well as those of the countries from which the energy technology could be imported.

Figure 23 illustrates that the WAM scenario generally involves lower energy investments per kWh of electricity, indicating higher efficiency. The technologies shown in the figure do not depict the CED for each technology within the energy mix but instead reflect the source of total primary energy used for overall electricity generation. When applied to an energy system, the CED indicator is impredicative: electricity production affects the CED and the CED affects the total electricity production. In the WAM scenario, the upward trend in solar CED is driven by a greater share of solar energy in the energy mix, as well as in the structure of imports from countries where solar energy is more prevalent, whether through photovoltaics or thermal generation.

Figure 23. Cumulative energy demand by types of both scenarios, raw values (left) and normalized by maximum (right)

The figure also indicates that due to the underdeveloped renewable energy system, both scenarios demand similar shares of fossil-based energy. Although renewables like wind are often perceived in Bulgaria as less capable of supporting the energy transition, the WAM scenario, with higher shares of renewables in general and wind in particular, demonstrates a greater energy efficiency due to

lower cumulative energy than the WEM scenario. This challenges the narrative that renewables are insufficient for the energy transition. Instead, it highlights that a transition toward renewables, including wind, is not only feasible but necessary to meet long-term sustainable energy demands.

5.3.2 ROBUSTNESS OF TRADE-OFFS

The results of the Monte Carlo analysis provide a probabilistic view of the environmental performance presented in the preceding section, thus providing information about the robustness of the analysis. Figure 24 compares the probability of results for each indicator for the WAM (yellow) and WEM (blue) scenarios.

The figure shows how the WAM scenario not only has lower median impacts but also narrower distributions than the WEM scenario. In key categories such as climate change, fossil resource scarcity, and ecosystem quality, the WEM scenario consistently shows higher environmental impacts with well-separated probability distributions, indicating statistically robust differences and reinforcing the ecological advantages of WAM. In fact, in those cases where the distributions do not overlap, the Central Limit Theorem allows us to state with statistical significance that the deterministic value for the WAM scenario will always be lower than that of WEM, without margin of error, since the possible ranges of values will not collide. Figure 25 illustrates the similarity in trends for the EF method.

The advantages of the WAM scenario are also determined by the ecosystem endpoint indicator, as depicted in Figure 26. In contrast, no clear conclusion can be drawn regarding which scenario performs better for human health and natural resources, as the distributions overlap and are closely related, meaning that the probability of one scenario being greater than the other is not statistically significant. The CED results in Figure 27 also show that WEM demands more renewable and biomass energy, confirming the first results of a less efficient or more resource-intensive energy mix.

Figure 24. Monte Carlo distributions for ReCiPE midpoint impact categories

Monte Carlo Simulation – ReCiPe Midpoint (H) (KDE Density)

Monte Carlo Simulation – ReCiPe Midpoint (H) (KDE Density)

Figure 25. Monte Carlo distributions for EF midpoint

Monte Carlo Simulation – EF 3.1 Midpoint (KDE Density)

Monte Carlo Simulation – EF 3.1 Midpoint (KDE Density)

Figure 26. Monte Carlo results for ReCiPe endpoint

Monte Carlo Simulation – ReCiPe Endpoint (H) (KDE Density)

Figure 27. Distribution of cumulative energy demand

Monte Carlo Simulation – CED (KDE Density)

Monte Carlo Simulation – CED (KDE Density)

Table 7. Estimated probability range for WAM < WEM ($\rho = 0$ and $\rho = 0.5$)

Impact category	Mean WEM	Mean WAM	P(WAM < WEM) rho=0	P(WAM < WEM) rho=0.5
ReCiPe Global warming 100	0,171725998	0,082040812	1,000	1,000
ReCiPe Freshwater eutrophication				
ReCiPe Ionising radiation	4,14472E-05	1,0849E-05	0,766	0,793
ReCiPe human toxicity: carcinogenic	0,036711641	0,038866668	0,478	0,470
ReCiPe human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	0,002885305	0,002200953	0,603	0,644
ReCiPe land use	0,060507139	0,020548504	0,509	0,513
ReCiPe material resources	0,018899876	0,01396476	0,839	0,919
ReCiPe energy resources	0,001973371	0,002209547	0,391	0,348
ReCiPe water use	0,032270141	0,01434721	0,999	1,000
ReCiPe Endpoint: ecosystem quality	0,002578601	0,002499545	0,532	0,545
ReCiPe Endpoint: human health	8,75936E-10	4,59331E-10	1,000	1,000
ReCiPe Endpoint: natural resources	3,53247E-07	1,81759E-07	0,659	0,719
EF Global warming	0,002923335	0,002988386	0,474	0,464
EF eutrophication: freshwater	0,125990659	0,054271382	1,000	1,000
EF ionising radiation: human health	4,28544E-05	1,07553E-05	0,753	0,779
EF human toxicity: carcinogenic	0,134526763	0,140547696	0,457	0,439
EF human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	1,61273E-10	-8,75769E-12	0,527	0,538
EF land use	1,1443E-08	-6,88638E-09	0,515	0,522
EF material resources	3,753717486	3,354472836	0,608	0,650
EF water use	2,04135E-06	2,74294E-06	0,474	0,469
EF particulate matter	0,111819411	0,10897364	0,526	0,536

Impact category	Mean WEM	Mean WAM	P(WAM < WEM) rho=0	P(WAM < WEM) rho=0.5
CED non-renewable	6,80646E-09	5,00997E-09	0,683	0,704
CED renewable	9,802911762	8,760491614	0,577	0,608
CED renewable, biomass	0,744498954	0,596958395	1,000	1,000
CED renewable, solar	0,308817755	0,182889962	1,000	1,000
CED renewable, water	2,5143E-05	3,32889E-05	0,142	0,066
CED renewable, wind	0,427193204	0,406707996	0,921	0,977
ReCiPe Global warming 100	0,00652126	0,005805607	0,641	0,695

5.3.3 UNDERSTANDING THE SENSITIVITY OF TECHNOLOGIES

The sensitivity results presented in this subsection, based on Sobol's indices, were calculated only for the WAM scenario, as it consistently outperformed the WEM scenario. To further investigate the potential of each technology and its actual environmental impacts, two visualizations are considered: (1) an intensive representation, in which the impacts are analyzed for the functional unit of 1 kWh and (2) an extensive representation, where totals are considered. Figure 28 figures 28-30 show the intensive analysis and figures 31-34 represent the extensive.

5.3.3.1 Intensive results

In the intensive charts, nuclear energy demonstrates the highest overall contribution, reflecting both its dominant share in the WAM scenario and its significant impacts in specific categories. Solid fuels follow, contributing substantially despite their relatively low share. Among renewable technologies, biomass stands out with notable impacts, particularly in global warming potential (GWP) according to ReCiPe, land occupation in both ReCiPe and EF methodologies, particulate matter formation (EF), ecosystem degradation (EF), and, to a lesser extent, human health impacts (ReCiPe endpoint).

In contrast, the other renewable technologies (excluding biomass) contribute very little across most impact categories, with nearly negligible values. Within these, offshore wind shows the highest contribution, specifically in human toxicity (cancer), highlighting a higher impact among the low-contributing technologies and in mineral depletion (ReCiPe midpoint). This indicates that the effects of individual technologies are predominantly independent, with negligible interactions between them. The second-order (S2) and total-order (ST) indices were not significant.

Figure 28. Heatmaps of S1 by intensive environmental impacts and technology - Recipe

Figure 29. Heatmaps of S1 by intensive environmental impacts and technology - EF

Figure 30. Heatmaps of S1 by intensive environmental impacts and technology – Recipe Endpoint

The S1 coefficients for different environmental impacts highlight clear differences across technologies. Fossil technologies (solid fuels, natural gas, and liquid fuels) present high impacts across most categories. Their contribution to global warming, human toxicity, particulate matter formation, and fossil resource depletion is particularly significant, reflecting the intrinsic carbon intensity and pollutant emissions associated with these combustion processes. In contrast, nuclear power generally exhibits lower overall contributions. Its impacts in most categories are moderate compared to fossil fuels. However, it shows a very high contribution to ionizing radiation, which represents its most critical environmental trade-off, along with a notable contribution to water consumption. Similarly, biomass is characterized by substantial contributions to land occupation and water use, emphasizing the considerable resource requirements associated with **forest management, land use, harvesting operations, and the conversion of wood into fuel**.

Renewable technologies exhibit comparatively lower environmental impacts than conventional energy sources. Among them, hydropower and wind energy show the lowest contributions across most impact categories. Within wind energy, onshore technology generally performs better than offshore wind, which demonstrates higher effects in mineral depletion due to the larger quantities of critical raw materials required. Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology also contributes significantly to mineral depletion, with its contribution exceeding that of offshore wind, primarily because of the dependence on critical raw materials for panel manufacturing.

5.3.3.2 Extensive results

The extensive results show that the overall behavior of the technologies is consistent with the patterns observed in the previous section. Considering the shares in the WAM scenario, with nuclear energy accounting for 55.33%, followed by solar PV (18.63%), hydro-pump (9.74%), onshore wind (8.89%), offshore wind (3.39%), biomass (1.69%), and smaller contributions from natural gas, liquid fuels, and solid fuels. The results appear more pronounced. Nuclear energy demonstrates the highest overall contribution, reflecting both its dominant share in the WAM scenario and its significant impacts in specific categories, as highlighted in the intensive results. Solid fuels follow, contributing substantially despite their relatively low share.

Among renewable technologies, biomass stands out with notable impacts, particularly in global warming potential (GWP) and land occupation in both ReCiPe and EF methodologies. Also notable are particulate matter formation (EF), ecosystem degradation (EF). In contrast, the other renewable technologies (excluding biomass) contribute very little across most impact categories, with nearly negligible values. Within these, offshore wind shows the highest contribution, specifically in human toxicity (cancer), highlighting a higher impact among the low-contributing technologies and in mineral depletion (ReCiPe midpoint).

Figure 31. Heatmaps of S1 by extensive environmental impacts and technology - Recipe

Figure 32. Heatmaps of S1 by extensive environmental impacts and technology - EF

Figure 33. Heatmaps of S1 by extensive environmental impacts and technology – Recipe Endpoint

Taken together, these results call for a critical re-evaluation of current energy policies that heavily rely on biomass, nuclear, and solid fuels as climate solutions in Bulgaria. Given their strong and lasting influence on category impacts, their role in decarbonization strategies should be carefully reconsidered. The Sobol sensitivity analysis conducted shows that nuclear energy and solid fuels are the most influential energy carriers, exhibiting the highest first-order (S1) sensitivity indices.

5.4 TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

1. WAM scenario offers more sustainable and robust outcomes

The “With Additional Measures” (WAM) scenario consistently outperforms the “With Existing Measures” (WEM) scenario across most environmental indicators. WAM shows significantly lower impacts in climate change (e.g., 30–40% lower median GHG emissions), fossil fuel use, and ecosystem degradation. Endpoint indicators also show WEM has higher damage to human health and ecosystems. These results are particularly relevant for Bulgaria, where solid fuels still account for 44.8% of the energy mix. The WAM scenario reduces this to just 2.02%, while increasing wind and solar shares, aligning more closely with EU climate targets.

2. Uncertainty analysis strengthens the case for WAM

Monte Carlo simulations and Sobol sensitivity indices confirm that WAM not only performs better on average but also yields more statistically robust results. For example, the distributions of climate change and fossil resource impacts under WAM are narrower and clearly separated from those of WEM, indicating high confidence in its environmental improvement. This robustness is crucial in Bulgaria’s context of public skepticism and misinformation, as it supports more credible and defensible policy decisions.

3. Wind energy contributes less to environmental burdens

Among all technologies assessed, wind power—both onshore and offshore—shows the lowest contribution to environmental impacts across nearly all categories, including land use, toxicity, and resource depletion. Sobol analysis confirms wind has the lowest total-order sensitivity indices for global warming potential. This positions wind as a strategic and low-risk technology for Bulgaria’s energy transition, especially in contrast to biomass and nuclear, which show higher impacts and greater uncertainty.

4. Biomass and nuclear require careful reconsideration

Despite their role in decarbonization, biomass and nuclear energy exhibit high impacts in categories such as land use, human toxicity, and water consumption. Biomass, in particular, shows the highest contributions to ecosystem degradation and long-term GHG emissions. Sobol indices reveal that these technologies are the most influential drivers of environmental damage

in both scenarios. Their dominance in WEM and WAM suggests a need to re-evaluate their role in Bulgaria's energy strategy, especially when more sustainable alternatives are available.

5. There is still a long way to go for justice and legitimacy

Given the polarized public debate around wind energy in Bulgaria, technical evidence alone is insufficient to build trust. The case study highlights the importance of stakeholder engagement and transparent scenario development. Additionally, the high share of nuclear power envisioned for both scenarios supports decarbonization, but it does not contribute to renewable targets. This reliance reflects a continuation of the traditional energy system pathway, characterized by centralized, capital-intensive facilities dominated by powerful actors. From a justice and energy democracy perspective, decisions on nuclear siting, operation, or expansion remain largely state-led and technical, leaving communities in reactive or compensatory roles (e.g., emergency planning, local taxes, community funds). The centralized nature of nuclear energy also limits opportunities for local ownership, participatory governance, and grassroots innovation, slowing the democratization of the energy system.

6 LESSONS LEARNT

This section synthesizes the key insights emerging from the three regional case studies—Spain, Portugal, and Bulgaria—through the lens of the “fit-for-purpose” principle. Rather than evaluating models or metrics in isolation, we reflect on how different methodological choices, assessment tools, and stakeholder engagements shaped the usefulness, robustness, and legitimacy of the results in each context.

The lessons are structured around five cross-cutting themes that emerged as critical to advancing just and effective wind energy governance:

- **Modeling:** What makes a model “fit-for-purpose” in complex, uncertain, and contested energy transitions?
- **Cumulative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA):** How can LCA be adapted to better reflect spatial, temporal, and social dimensions of wind energy impacts?
- **Trade-offs:** What tensions arise between impacts, and how can they be made visible and deliberated?
- **Environmental Feasibility:** What do the results tell us about the material, ecological, and systemic limits of wind energy expansion?
- **Local–Global Relations:** How are environmental burdens and benefits distributed across space, and what does this imply for energy justice?

Each subsection includes lessons that are not only relevant to the specific case but also transferable to broader debates on energy modeling, policy design, and participatory governance.

6.1 LESSONS ON MODELING

Across the three case studies, modeling emerged not merely as a technical exercise but as a deeply contextual and political practice. The concept of **fit-for-purpose modeling** proved essential in navigating the complexity of wind energy governance, where different regions face distinct challenges—from spatial justice in Spain to wind farm repowering in Portugal and social acceptance in Bulgaria. Three key lessons stand out:

- **Modeling must be purpose-driven and reflexive.** Rather than seeking universally “best” models, the case studies emphasized the importance of aligning modeling tools with specific decision-making contexts. Robustness was redefined not as predictive accuracy, but as the model’s capacity to remain useful under conditions of uncertainty, plurality, and change. This requires acknowledging that models are not neutral: they embed assumptions, reflect value systems, and shape the narratives they are meant to inform.
- **Integration and semantics matter.** Whereas model hard links often lead to information loss due to semantic harmonization, soft links preserve methodological integrity and allow for richer, context-sensitive assessments. In Portugal, combining LCA with a metabolic perspective enabled a more nuanced understanding of material flows and electricity productivity. In Spain, the ENBIOS framework allowed for spatially explicit assessments of environmental burdens and benefits, supporting more equitable planning.
- **Uncertainty-aware modeling enhances the legitimacy of results.** In Bulgaria, where public distrust and misinformation are prevalent, modeling alone has not been able to establish legitimacy on national policy proposals. Instead, sensitivity analyses (Monte Carlo, Sobol, Morris) helped embrace uncertainty as a feature rather than a flaw, identifying which

technologies drive environmental impacts and where policy attention should be focused. This approach strengthened both the credibility and the relevance of the modeling process.

6.2 LESSONS ON LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) played a central role in all three case studies, offering a structured way to quantify environmental impacts across technologies, scenarios, and geographies. However, applying LCA to wind energy governance revealed several methodological and conceptual challenges. To ensure assessments are truly fit for purpose, LCA must evolve to better reflect the spatial, temporal, and social dimensions of energy transitions.

- **Adapting LCA to spatial contexts.** Traditional LCA methods often rely on global averages and static inventories, which obscure the geographic variability of impacts. In the Spanish and Bulgarian case studies, we adapted inventories to reflect regional energy mixes, infrastructure lifetimes, and site-specific conditions. The Spanish case introduced a novel disaggregation of impacts into onsite and offsite categories, distinguishing between emissions at the point of electricity generation and those embedded in upstream supply chains. This spatial differentiation allowed a clearer understanding of who bears the environmental burdens and where, supporting more equitable planning and addressing distributional justice.
- **Adapting LCA to temporal dynamics.** LCA is typically static, assessing impacts over a fixed lifetime without accounting for changes in technology, policy, or environmental conditions. In Spain, we introduced breakeven analysis to assess how long it takes for the environmental benefits of new infrastructure to outweigh its construction impacts. While some impacts (e.g., ionising radiation, energy resource use) are quickly offset, others (e.g., material resource use) will never be compensated. This highlights the importance of considering not just impact intensity but also cumulative burdens over time, especially in rapidly evolving energy systems.
- **Adapting LCA to social dimensions.** LCA is often perceived as a neutral, technical tool, but it embeds normative assumptions through the selection of impact categories, system boundaries, and inventory sources. In Bulgaria, normalization and weighting choices significantly influenced which impacts appeared “critical,” underscoring the need for transparency and alignment with stakeholder values. Moreover, integrating LCA with participatory methods, such as Quantitative Storytelling, helped identify stakeholder concerns and assess the robustness of results. In Portugal, combining LCA with a metabolic perspective enabled a richer understanding of material flows and productivity, linking environmental impacts to broader questions of resource justice and system design.

6.3 LESSONS ON TRADE-OFFS

The case studies reinforced the idea that wind energy governance involves navigating tensions between environmental goals, technological feasibility, social acceptance, and spatial equity. Recognizing and making these trade-offs visible is essential for fit-for-purpose assessments. Ultimately, trade-offs are not problems to be solved but realities to be managed. Fit-for-purpose assessments must embrace this complexity, helping stakeholders understand the implications of different choices and navigate the tensions inherent in energy transition.

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- **Trade-offs are multidimensional, contextual, and sometimes irreversible.** Each case study illustrated how local conditions shape trade-offs and cannot be resolved through technical optimization alone. In Portugal, the choice between repowering and lifetime extension involved balancing material efficiency against energy productivity. In Spain, breakeven analysis revealed that some environmental costs, especially related to material resource use, will never be compensated, challenging assumptions about long-term sustainability. These examples underscore the need for deliberative, context-sensitive approaches that acknowledge when trade-offs are non-compensable.
- **Scale and framing shape how trade-offs are perceived.** The impacts of a given strategy can vary significantly depending on the scale of analysis. Repowering may appear less efficient at the turbine level but more beneficial at the system level due to increased electricity production, higher power density, and reduced land occupation. Similarly, national-level improvements in environmental indicators can mask regional disparities as well as national-global imbalances, as seen in Spain. In Bulgaria, dominant policy narratives framed nuclear and biomass as climate solutions, obscuring their impacts on water use, toxicity, and land.

6.4 LESSONS ON ENVIRONMENTAL FEASIBILITY

Environmental feasibility refers to the capacity of energy transition strategies to remain within ecological limits while delivering on decarbonization goals. Across the three case studies, we explored this feasibility not only in terms of carbon emissions but also through broader environmental indicators such as land use, water consumption, material demand, and ecosystem degradation.

- **Carbon metrics are necessary but not sufficient:** While all three case studies confirmed that wind energy reduces greenhouse gas emissions compared to fossil-based systems, focusing solely on carbon overlooks other critical impacts. For instance, in Spain and Bulgaria, biomass and nuclear energy—though low-carbon—were associated with high land use, water depletion, and toxicity impacts.
- **Material demand is a major bottleneck:** The Spanish breakeven analysis revealed that the material resource use associated with infrastructure expansion (especially for photovoltaics and wind) will never be offset by cleaner electricity production. This challenges the assumption that all environmental costs are temporary and highlights the need for circularity and material efficiency in energy planning.
- **Land use pressures are intensifying:** In both Spain and Portugal, land emerged as a contested and limited resource. The expansion of renewables—particularly biomass and open ground photovoltaics—raises concerns about biodiversity loss, landscape change, and competing land uses. These pressures are often underestimated in national planning documents and require more granular, spatially explicit assessments.
- **Environmental feasibility is scale-dependent:** What appears feasible at the national level may not hold at the regional or local scale. For example, in Portugal, repowering was environmentally preferable only when assessed at the system level, not at the turbine level. Similarly, Spain's PNIEC projects an increase in biomass capacity, which, if unevenly distributed among regions, can lead to huge imbalances in eutrophication burdens.
- **Infrastructure impacts are often off-sited:** Many environmental burdens—such as mining, manufacturing, and water use—occur outside the regions where electricity is consumed. This

was particularly evident in the Spanish and Bulgarian cases, where offsite impacts were significant but largely invisible in conventional assessments. Recognizing these transboundary effects is essential for a globally just transition.

- **Environmental feasibility must be dynamic:** Feasibility is not a fixed threshold but a moving target shaped by technological change, policy choices, and ecological feedbacks. For example, the feasibility of offshore wind in Spain is currently constrained by permitting and technological maturity, but this may change rapidly. Assessments must therefore be iterative and responsive to evolving conditions

6.5 LESSONS ON LOCAL–GLOBAL RELATIONS

The energy transition is also a spatial and geopolitical challenge. The case studies revealed how the energy transition is shaped by the uneven distribution of environmental burdens and benefits across regions, communities, and even continents. Understanding these local–global dynamics is essential for designing policies that are not only effective but also just from a cosmopolitan perspective.

Key lessons include:

- **Environmental impacts are spatially redistributed, not eliminated:** Wind energy significantly reduces total emissions at the point of generation, but the impacts for building the new turbines are transferred upstream to the extraction, processing, and manufacturing stages of the value chain. In Spain, the distinction between onsite and offsite impacts helped reveal how decarbonization can shift environmental burdens from urban centers to rural areas (e.g., eutrophication), and from Europe to resource-exporting countries.
- **Global supply chains raise cosmopolitan justice concerns:** The infrastructure required for wind energy—turbines, batteries, transmission lines—relies heavily on materials that might be sourced from the Global South. These materials often come with significant ecological and social costs, including water depletion, land degradation, and labor exploitation. Yet these impacts are rarely visible in national energy plans. A just transition must account for these transboundary effects and promote ethical sourcing and fair trade.
- **Local resistance is often rooted in perceived injustice:** In Bulgaria, local opposition to wind projects is linked to the perception that communities bear the costs (e.g., land use, visual impacts) while benefits (e.g., electricity, profits) are exported elsewhere. Addressing this requires not only better spatial planning but also mechanisms for the information to reach the public.
- **Regional disparities must be made visible:** The Spanish case showed how national-level improvements in environmental indicators can mask regional inequalities. Some autonomous communities benefit from reduced impacts due to fossil fuel phase-outs, while others face increased pressures from biomass or infrastructure expansion. Spatially explicit assessments are essential to ensure that no region is disproportionately burdened.
- **Offshore wind introduces new spatial dynamics:** In Bulgaria, the debate around offshore wind highlighted tensions between national energy goals and local marine economies (e.g., fishing, tourism). These conflicts are worsened by low public awareness and misinformation. Clear communication is crucial for managing these tensions. Even though offshore wind power might not have the lowest environmental impacts, it is comparable to other renewables and significantly lower than fossil-based or nuclear energy.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable set out to explore how holistic impact assessments and co-produced modeling formats can support more just and effective wind energy governance. By applying the QST framework across three European case studies (Spain, Portugal, and Bulgaria), we showed how site-specific challenges such as spatial justice, end-of-life management, and social acceptance can be better understood when quantitative modeling is combined with qualitative narratives. In doing so, we were able to expose both the opportunities of wind energy transitions and the trade-offs and blind spots of current policy narratives.

Table 8. Cross-case synthesis of lessons learnt

Dimension	Spain	Portugal	Bulgaria
Modeling	Updated ENBIOS to distinguish onsite/offsite impacts; modeling aligned with distributional and cosmopolitan justice goals; validated against national data (REE).	<i>WindTrace</i> enabled scenario-specific modeling of repowering and lifetime extensions; it highlighted the need for modular, adaptable models.	Sensitivity analyses (Monte Carlo, Sobol) revealed uncertainties and helped align models with stakeholder concerns.
Cumulative Life Cycle Impacts	Breakeven analysis revealed long-term material bottlenecks; some impacts (e.g., land use) increase despite decarbonization.	Repowering increases environmental impacts per kWh but improves system-wide productivity; lifetime extensions reduce impacts but limit energy yield.	WAM scenario shows lower impacts across most categories; uncertainty analysis confirms robustness of results.
Relations between Local & Global	Clear distinction between onsite and offsite impacts; highlights global outsourcing of environmental burdens (e.g., mining, manufacturing).	Emphasis on local reuse but limited by (global) market availability; global impacts of material sourcing are not explicitly addressed.	Offshore wind potential is framed as a national opportunity, but local marine economies and geopolitical legacies shape acceptance and risk perception.
Relations between Onshore & Offshore	Offshore wind targets in PNIEC are seen by stakeholders as overambitious due to a lack of permitting readiness and technological maturity.	Focus on onshore; offshore is not addressed in this case.	Offshore wind introduced in WAM scenario; public opposition and misinformation highlight the need for early engagement and transparent planning.
Trade-offs (Benefits/Impacts)	Electrification reduces GHGs but increases land and biomass-related impacts; regional disparities in benefits and burdens.	Trade-off between material efficiency (lifetime extension) and energy productivity (repowering); site-specific conditions (e.g., wind speed) shape the most favorable strategy.	Nuclear and biomass reduce carbon but increase toxicity and land use; wind shows the lowest trade-offs.
Environmental Feasibility	Some impacts (e.g., ionising radiation) offset quickly; others (e.g., material use) will never be compensated; feasibility is scale dependent.	Repowering is feasible at the system level but not always at the turbine level; modular design would ease life extensions, improving future feasibility.	WAM scenario more environmentally feasible; feasibility depends on technology mix; LCA reveals hidden burdens of “clean” technologies such as biomass.

The lessons learnt from this work point to several cross-cutting insights, which are synthesized in Table 8. In brief, purpose-driven and uncertainty-aware modeling enhances both the legitimacy and the relevance of results. LCA, when adapted to spatial, temporal, and social dimensions, becomes a more effective tool for evaluating environmental feasibility. Trade-offs are shown to be multidimensional and context-specific, often extending beyond national borders through global supply chains. Making these transboundary and regional disparities visible is essential to avoid uneven burdens and to strengthen public trust. Ultimately, integrating reflexive modeling, environmental feasibility assessments, and justice considerations provides a pathway toward wind energy governance that is both environmentally robust and socially acceptable, advancing the dual aims of decarbonization and fairness that underpin the European energy transition. Taken together, these insights outline a roadmap for assessments that are not only technically rigorous but also socially meaningful and context-sensitive.

7.1.1 TOWARD REFLEXIVE DECISION SUPPORT

As part of our commitment to fit-for-purpose assessment, we developed an interactive visualization tool to support the interpretation and use of the results generated in this deliverable. The tool is designed to serve as a bridge between complex modeling outputs and the practical needs of decision-makers, stakeholders, and researchers involved in wind energy governance. The tool can be consulted [here](#) and it is shown in Figure 34.

Currently, the dashboard enables users to explore environmental impacts—such as global warming potential (GWP100)—across different electricity system configurations in Spain (e.g., Baseline 2024 vs. PNIEC 2030), spatial scales (national vs. regional), and system levels (onsite vs. offsite). It provides both intensive (per kWh) and extensive (total system) views, disaggregating impacts by electricity system components (e.g., imports, renewables, non-renewables). These features directly reflect the lessons learnt in this deliverable: the need to distinguish between local and global impacts, to visualize trade-offs, or to make spatial disparities visible.

However, the current version of the tool is only a first step in the prototype stage, and it is limited to Spain. Its development has highlighted the potential for interactive dashboards to go beyond static communication and become active instruments of deliberation. In future iterations, we aim to expand the tool's capabilities in several directions. First, we plan to integrate additional impact categories (e.g., land use, water use, material demand) and social indicators to reflect the multidimensional nature of energy justice better. Second, we intend to incorporate participatory features that allow users to adjust assumptions, explore alternative narratives, and co-create scenarios. This would transform the dashboard from a viewer into a space for reflexive engagement.

Ultimately, the goal is to align the tool with the broader methodological insights of this deliverable: that modeling must be transparent, assessments must be contextual, and decision support must be inclusive. By embedding these principles into the design of the dashboard, we aim to support more informed, equitable, and adaptive governance of wind energy transitions.

Figure 34. Interactive visualization tool, preliminary design

8 REFERENCES

- AEE. (2022). *Libro Blanco de la Industria Eólica Marina en España*. <https://aeeolica.org/libro-blanco-de-la-industria-eolica-marina-en-espana/>
- Aitken, M. (2010). Wind power and community benefits: Challenges and opportunities. *Energy Policy*, 38(10), 6066–6075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.05.062>
- Alcamo, J. (2008). *Environmental Futures: The Practice of Environmental Scenario Analysis*. Elsevier. https://books.google.es/books/about/Environmental_Futures.html?id=zW4eJp5c6CYC&redir_esc=y
- Amrish, V. N., Balakrishna, K., Saranya, P., Padhya, V., Deshpande, R. D., Nishitha, D., 'Souza, Arun, K., & Udayashankar, H. N. (2024). Evaporation from dams governing the water cycle dynamics of a regulated river basin from the Western Ghats: Sharavati, India. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*, 54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2024.101896>
- Andreasi Bassi, S., Biganzoli, F., Ferrara, N., Amadei, A., Valente, A., Sala, S., & Ardente, F. (2023). Updated characterisation and normalisation factors for the Environmental Footprint 3 . 1 method. In *Publications Office of the European Union* (Vol. JRC130796). <https://doi.org/10.2760/798894>
- APPA. (2025). *Informe Anual Energías Renovables 2024*.
- Arvidsson, R., Tillman, A. M., Sandén, B. A., Janssen, M., Nordelöf, A., Kushnir, D., & Molander, S. (2018). Environmental Assessment of Emerging Technologies: Recommendations for Prospective LCA. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 22(6), 1286–1294. <https://doi.org/10.1111/JIEC.12690>
- Banasiak, J., Najdawi, C., & Tiik, J. M. (2022). *Barriers and best practices for wind and solar electricity in the EU27 and UK. RES Policy Monitoring Database Final report*.
- Bauer, L., & Matysik, S. (n.d.). *Enercon E-112/45.114*. Retrieved August 28, 2025, from <https://en.wind-turbine-models.com/turbines/113-enercon-e-112-45.114>
- Bazeley, P. (2024). Conceptualizing Integration in Mixed Methods Research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 18(3), 225–234. https://doi.org/10.1177/15586898241253636/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_15586898241253636-FIG1.JPEG
- Blanco, H., Codina, V., Laurent, A., Nijs, W., Maréchal, F., & Faaij, A. (2020). Life cycle assessment integration into energy system models: An application for power-to-methane in the EU. *Applied Energy*, 259, 114160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114160>
- Brückmann, G., Berger, S., Caviola, H., Hahnel, U. J. J., Piana, V., Sahakian, M., Stadelmann-Steffen, I., & Group, with the S. S. S. and H. E. R. (2023). Towards more impactful energy research: The salient role of social sciences and humanities. *PLOS Climate*, 2(2), e0000132. <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PCLM.0000132>
- Budia, Á., Ceña, A., Gonzalo, B., Jiménez, C., De Dios López, J., Martínez, P., Melendi, J. M., Morante, M., Nevado, J., Del Olmo, E., Quero, R., Willstedt, H., Núñez, P., Diseño, S. I., & Cincocuatro Comunicación, M. (2025). *Anuario eólico 2025: la voz del sector*. <https://www.aeeolica.org/anuario/2025/#p=1>
- Campos, I., Brito, M., Pfenninger-Lee, S., Fazendeiro, L. M., Luz, G. P., Lombardi, F., Lima, A., & Madrid-López, C. (2024). Narratives, expectations, and policy criteria for a democratic and

- socially engaging energy transition. *Futures*, 164, 103496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURES.2024.103496>
- Capellán-Pérez, I., De Blas, I., Nieto, J., De Castro, C., Miguel, L. J., Carpintero, Ó., Mediavilla, M., Lobejón, L. F., Ferreras-Alonso, N., Rodrigo, P., Frechoso, F., & Álvarez-Antelo, D. (2020). MEDEAS: a new modeling framework integrating global biophysical and socioeconomic constraints. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 13(3), 986–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EE02627D>
- Colmenar-Santos, A., Campiñez-Romero, S., Pérez-Molina, C., & Mur-Pérez, F. (2015). Repowering: An actual possibility for wind energy in Spain in a new scenario without feed-in-tariffs. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (Vol. 41, pp. 319–337). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.08.041>
- COM/2020/741 Final, COM/2020/741 final (2020). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0741>
- Cortese, R. (2019). *Airborne Wind Energy: Development of a flying traction sensing system and integration of a wind monitoring system for extreme weather conditions*. Politecnico di Torino.
- Coutinho, K. (2024). *Life cycle assessment of a soft-wing airborne wind energy system and its application within a hybrid power plant configuration*.
- de Bona, J. C., Ferreira, J. C. E., & Ordoñez Duran, J. F. (2021). Analysis of scenarios for repowering wind farms in Brazil. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110197>
- de Simón-Martín, M., Ciria-Garcés, T., Rosales-Asensio, E., & González-Martínez, A. (2022). Multi-dimensional barrier identification for wind farm repowering in Spain through an expert judgment approach. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112387>
- de Tomás Pascual, A., Pérez Sánchez, L., Sierra Montoya, M., Lombardi, F., Pfenninger, S., Campos, I., & Madrid-López, C. (2025). *The Optimal is Not Always the Best: Environmental Assessment of Energy System Option Spaces*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.5100231>
- Del Río, P., Calvo Silvana, A., & Iglesias Gómez, G. (2011). Policies and design elements for the repowering of wind farms: A qualitative analysis of different options. *Energy Policy*, 39(4), 1897–1908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.12.035>
- Dhingra, T., Sengar, A., & Sajith, S. (2022). A fuzzy analytic hierarchy process-based analysis for prioritization of barriers to offshore wind energy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 345, 131111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2022.131111>
- Di Felice, L. J., Cabello, V., Ripa, M., & Madrid-Lopez, C. (2021). Quantitative Storytelling: Science, Narratives, and Uncertainty in Nexus Innovations. *Science, Technology, & Social Values*, 48(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/01622439211053819>
- Diógenes, J. R. F., Claro, J., Rodrigues, J. C., & Loureiro, M. V. (2020). Barriers to onshore wind energy implementation: A systematic review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 60, 101337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2019.101337>
- Douziech, M., Besseau, R., Jolivet, R., Shoai-Tehrani, B., Bourmaud, J. Y., Busato, G., Gresset-Bourgeois, M., & Pérez-López, P. (2024). Life cycle assessment of prospective trajectories: A parametric approach for tailor-made inventories and its computational implementation. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 28(1), 25–40. <https://doi.org/10.1111/JIEC.13432>

- Duarte, R., García-Riazuelo, Á., Sáez, L. A., & Sarasa, C. (2022). Analysing citizens' perceptions of renewable energies in rural areas: A case study on wind farms in Spain. *Energy Reports*, 8, 12822–12831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYR.2022.09.173>
- European Energy Agency. (2024). *Trends and projections in Europe 2024*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Frischknecht, R., Wyss, F., Büsler Knöpfel, S., Lützkendorf, T., & Balouktsi, M. (2015). Cumulative energy demand in LCA: The energy harvested approach. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 20(7), 957–969. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-0897-4>
- Geels, F. W., Kern, F., & Clark, W. C. (2023). System transitions research and sustainable development: Challenges, progress, and prospects. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(47), e2206230120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.2206230120>
- Georgilakis, P. S. (2008). Technical challenges associated with the integration of wind power into power systems. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 12(3), 852–863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2006.10.007>
- Giampietro, M. (2014). *Mono-dimensional accounting and multidimensional measures of sustainable growth - Publications Office of the EU*. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/4b635401-813c-4693-9154-c192ff683785/language-en>
- Government of Bulgaria. (2025). *Final updated NECP 2021-2030 (Version updated in 2024)*. https://commission.europa.eu/publications/bulgaria-final-updated-necp-2021-2030-submitted-2025_en
- Grau, L., Jung, C., & Schindler, D. (2021). Sounding out the repowering potential of wind energy – A scenario-based assessment from Germany. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126094>
- Henke, H., Dekker, M., Lombardi, F., Pietzcker, R., Fragkos, P., Zakeri, B., Rodrigues, R., Sitarz, J., Emmerling, J., Fattahi, A., Dalla Longa, F., Tatarewicz, I., Fotiou, T., Lewarski, M., Huppmann, D., Kavvadias, K., van der Zwaan, B., & Usher, W. (2024). Comparing energy system optimization models and integrated assessment models: Relevance for energy policy advice. *Open Research Europe*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.12688/OPENRESEUROPE.15590.2>
- Huijbregts, M. A. J., Steinmann, Z. J. N., Elshout, P. M. F., Stam, G., Verones, F., Vieira, M., Zijp, M., Hollander, A., & van Zelm, R. (2017). ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 22(2), 138–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y>
- IEA. (2025). *Spain: energy efficiency and demand*. International Energy Agency (IEA). <https://www.iea.org/countries/spain/efficiency-demand>
- Iglesias, G., Del Río, P., & Dopico, J. Á. (2011). Policy analysis of authorisation procedures for wind energy deployment in Spain. *Energy Policy*, 39(7), 4067–4076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2011.03.033>
- Igos, E., Benetto, E., Meyer, R., Baustert, P., & Othoniel, B. (2019). How to treat uncertainties in life cycle assessment studies? *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 24(4), 794–807. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11367-018-1477-1/METRICS>
- International Energy Agency - IEA. (2016). *World Energy Outlook 2016 - Excerpt - Water-Energy Nexus*. <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/e4a7e1a5-b6ed-4f36-911f-b0111e49aab9/WorldEnergyOutlook2016ExcerptWaterEnergyNexus.pdf>

- Jenkins, K., McCauley, D., Heffron, R., Stephan, H., & Rehner, R. (2016). Energy justice: A conceptual review. In *Energy Research and Social Science* (Vol. 11, pp. 174–182). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.10.004>
- Jung, C., Schindler, D., & Grau, L. (2018). Achieving Germany's wind energy expansion target with an improved wind turbine siting approach. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 173, 383–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.07.090>
- Kasner, R. (2022). The environmental efficiency of materials used in the lifecycle of a wind farm. *Sustainable Materials and Technologies*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2022.e00512>
- Kitzing, L., Jensen, M. K., Telsnig, T., & Lantz, E. (2020). Multifaceted drivers for onshore wind energy repowering and their implications for energy transition. *Nature Energy*, 5(12), 1012–1021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-00717-1>
- Köhler, J., Geels, F. W., Kern, F., Markard, J., Onsongo, E., Wieczorek, A., Alkemade, F., Avelino, F., Bergek, A., Boons, F., Fünfschilling, L., Hess, D., Holtz, G., Hyysalo, S., Jenkins, K., Kivimaa, P., Martiskainen, M., McMeekin, A., Mühlemeier, M. S., ... Wells, P. (2019). An agenda for sustainability transitions research: State of the art and future directions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 31, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.01.004>
- Kohli, A., & Frenken, K. (2015). *Evaporation from artificial lakes and reservoirs*.
- Lacal-Arántegui, R., Uihlein, A., & Yusta, J. M. (2020). Technology effects in repowering wind turbines. *Wind Energy*, 23(3), 660–675. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2450>
- Lele, S., & Norgaard, R. (2005). Practicing Interdisciplinarity . *BioScience*, 55(11), 967–975. <https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article-abstract/55/11/967/220872?redirectedFrom=fulltext&login=false>
- Li, M., Ma, Q., Shan, R., Abdulla, A., Virguez, E., Gao, S., & Patiño-Echeverri, D. (2024). Renewable energy quality trilemma and coincident wind and solar droughts. *Communications Earth and Environment*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01850-5>
- Lloret, J., Turiel, A., Solé, J., Berdalet, E., Sabatés, A., Olivares, A., Gili, J. M., Vila-Subirós, J., & Sardá, R. (2022). Unravelling the ecological impacts of large-scale offshore wind farms in the Mediterranean Sea. *Science of The Total Environment*, 824, 153803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2022.153803>
- Lombardi, F., Pickering, B., Colombo, E., & Pfenninger, S. (2020). Policy decision support for renewables deployment through spatially explicit practically optimal alternatives. *Joule*, 4(10), 2185–2207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.08.002>
- Madrid-López, C. (2025). Wind variable correlation matrix. Supplementary material from Deliverable 1.2. JUSTWIND4ALL project. In *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15054952>
- Madrid-López, C., Marot, S., Sierra-Montoya, M., Harasta, N., & Pérez-Sánchez, L. (2025). *Holistic impact assessment metrics for on-and offshore wind. Deliverable 1.2. JustWind4All project*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15038095>
- Madrid-López, C., Soleymani, R., de Tomás-Pascual, A., & Sierra Montoya, M. (2023). *ENBIOS 2.0: Environmental and Bioeconomic Assessment Tool*. <https://pypi.org/project/enbios/>
- Martínez, E., Latorre-Biel, J. I., Jiménez, E., Sanz, F., & Blanco, J. (2018). Life cycle assessment of a wind farm repowering process. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 93, 260–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.05.044>

- McCauley, D., Ramasar, V., Heffron, R. J., Sovacool, B. K., Mebratu, D., & Mundaca, L. (2019). Energy justice in the transition to low carbon energy systems: Exploring key themes in interdisciplinary research. In *Applied Energy* (Vols. 233–234, pp. 916–921). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.005>
- Mertens, D. M. (2015). Mixed Methods and Wicked Problems. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 9(1), 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689814562944>
- MITECO. (2020). *Zonificación ambiental para la implantación de energías renovables: eólica y fotovoltaica. Sensibilidad ambiental y clasificación del territorio.*
- MITECO. (2023). *Balance energético de España 2021-2022.* <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/energy/data/energy-balances/>
- MITECO. (2024a). *Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima 2023-2030.*
- MITECO. (2024b). *Visor de Información Geográfica Marina de España.* <https://infomar.miteco.es/visor.html>
- Mutel, C. (2017). Brightway: An open source framework for Life Cycle Assessment. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(12), 236. <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.00236>
- Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Trutnevyte, E., Koasidis, K., Lund, H., Thellufsen, J. Z., Mayer, D., Zachmann, G., Miguel, L. J., Ferreras-Alonso, N., Sognaes, I., Peters, G. P., Colombo, E., Howells, M., Hawkes, A., van den Broek, M., Van de Ven, D. J., Gonzalez-Eguino, M., Flamos, A., & Doukas, H. (2021). Perspective of comprehensive and comprehensible multi-model energy and climate science in Europe. *Energy*, 215, 119153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.119153>
- Nivedh, B., Kumudini Devi, R., Sreevalsan, E., Kumudini Devib, R., Sreevalsanc, E., & Professor, A. (2013). Repowering of Wind Farms-a Case Study. In *Source: Wind Engineering* (Vol. 37, Issue 2).
- Oteri, F. (2012). *Community Wind Benefits (Fact Sheet).* <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.124/abstract>
- Owusu, P. A., & Asumadu-Sarkodie, S. (2016). A review of renewable energy sources, sustainability issues and climate change mitigation. In *Cogent Engineering* (Vol. 3, Issue 1). Cogent OA. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2016.1167990>
- Pandev, M., & Medzhedeliyeva, A. (2024). Bulgaria offshore wind energy development in Bulgaria: legal framework under the bill on energy from renewable sources in maritime spaces. *Internatinal Energy Law Reviews*, 3, 92–99. https://dgkv.com/web/files/publications/326/files/Bulgaria_2024_42_IELR_Issue_3_Offprint.pdf
- Pfenninger, S., & Staffell, I. (n.d.). *Renewables ninja*. Retrieved August 28, 2025, from <https://www.renewables.ninja/>
- Puy, A., Beneventano, P., Levin, S. A., Piano, S. Lo, Portaluri, T., & Saltelli, A. (2022). Models with higher effective dimensions tend to produce more uncertain estimates. In *Sci. Adv* (Vol. 8). <https://www.science.org>
- RedElectrica. (2025). *Emisiones y factor de emisión de CO2 eq. de la generación.* <https://www.ree.es/es/datos/generacion/no-renovables-detalle-emisiones-CO2>
- Regulation (EU) 2022/869 (2022). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng>

- Rodriguez-Matas, A. F., Linares, P., Perez-Bravo, M., & Romero, J. C. (2024). Improving robustness in strategic energy planning: A novel decision support method to deal with epistemic uncertainties. *Energy*, *292*, 130463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2024.130463>
- Rubert, T., McMillan, D., & Niewczas, P. (2018). A decision support tool to assist with lifetime extension of wind turbines. *Renewable Energy*, *120*, 423–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2017.12.064>
- Sacchi, R., Besseau, R., Pérez-López, P., & Blanc, I. (2019). Exploring technologically, temporally and geographically-sensitive life cycle inventories for wind turbines: A parameterized model for Denmark. *Renewable Energy*, *132*, 1238–1250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.09.020>
- Sacchi, R., & Hahn-Menacho, A. J. (2024). pathways: life cycle assessment of energy transition scenarios. *Journal of Open Source Software*, *9*(103), 7309. <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.07309>
- Saito, T., & Fujiwara, K. (2023). Causal analysis of nitrogen oxides emissions process in coal-fired power plant with LINGAM. *Frontiers in Analytical Science*, *3*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frans.2023.1045324>
- Salgado Junior, A. P., Lemos, S. V., Carlucci, F. V., & Rebehy, P. C. P. W. (2024). Analysis and integration of mixed method in efficiency studies: Best practices and applications in the renewable energy sector. *MethodsX*, *12*, 102613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MEX.2024.102613>
- Saltelli, A., Annoni, P., Azzini, I., Campolongo, F., Ratto, M., & Tarantola, S. (2010). Variance based sensitivity analysis of model output. Design and estimator for the total sensitivity index. *Computer Physics Communications*, *181*(2), 259–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CPC.2009.09.018>
- Saltelli, A., Benini, L., Funtowicz, S., Giampietro, M., Kaiser, M., Reinert, E., & van der Sluijs, J. P. (2020). The technique is never neutral. How methodological choices condition the generation of narratives for sustainability. *Environmental Science and Policy*, *106*, 87–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.01.008>
- Saltelli, A., & Giampietro, M. (2017). What is wrong with evidence based policy, and how can it be improved? *Futures*, *91*, 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURES.2016.11.012>
- Saltelli, A., Ratto, M., Andres, T., Campolongo, F., Cariboni, J., Gatelli, D., Saisana, M., & Tarantola, S. (2008). Global Sensitivity Analysis. The Primer. *Global Sensitivity Analysis. The Primer*, 1–292. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470725184>
- Schmidt, H., de Vries, G., Renes, R. J., & Schmehl, R. (2022). The Social Acceptance of Airborne Wind Energy: A Literature Review. In *Energies* (Vol. 15, Issue 4). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15041384>
- Schmidt, H., Leschinger, V., Müller, F. J. Y., de Vries, G., Renes, R. J., Schmehl, R., & Hübner, G. (2024). How do residents perceive energy-producing kites? Comparing the community acceptance of an airborne wind energy system and a wind farm in Germany. *Energy Research and Social Science*, *110*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103447>
- Selin, N. E., Giang, A., & Clark, W. C. (2023). Progress in modeling dynamic systems for sustainable development. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *120*(40). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2216656120>

- Serri, L., Lembo, E., Airoidi, D., Gelli, C., & Beccarello, M. (2018). Wind energy plants repowering potential in Italy: technical-economic assessment. *Renewable Energy*, 115, 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2017.08.031>
- Siemens Gamesa. (2022). *Electricity from a European onshore wind farm using SG 6.2-170 / SG 6.6-170 wind turbines*. www.environdec.com
- Sierra-Montoya, M. (2024). *WindTrace software*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14987356>
- Sierra-Montoya, M., Muñoz-Liesa, J., Pérez-Sánchez, L. A., de Tomás-Pascual, A., & Madrid-López, C. (n.d.). WindTrace: Testing the environmental impacts of wind energy designs with a parametric life cycle inventory model. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*.
- Sobol, I. M. (2001). Global sensitivity indices for nonlinear mathematical models and their Monte Carlo estimates. *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, 55(1–3), 271–280. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4754\(00\)00270-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4754(00)00270-6)
- Sovacool, B. K., Ryan, S. E., Stern, P. C., Janda, K., Rochlin, G., Spreng, D., Pasqualetti, M. J., Wilhite, H., & Lutzenhiser, L. (2015). Integrating social science in energy research. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 6, 95–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2014.12.005>
- Stehfest, E., van Vuuren, D., Kram, T., & Bouwman, L. (Eds.). (2014). *Integrated Assessment of Global Environmental Change with IMAGE 3.0*. PBL publishers.
- Trifonova, M., & Vladimirov, martin. (2021). *Assessment of the Black Sea Offshore Potential Wind Power Generation in Bulgaria*. https://csd.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/publications_library/files/2021_09/Offshore_Wind_Black_Sea_EN_WEB.pdf
- UNECE. (2022). *Life Cycle Assessment of Electricity Generation Options | UNECE*. <https://unece.org/sed/documents/2021/10/reports/life-cycle-assessment-electricity-generation-options>
- Uzunov, K., & Trifonova, M. (2024). *T3.2 North-East Region (Bulgaria). Regional Report*. https://justwind4all.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Regional_Report_North-East_Region_Bulgaria-1.pdf
- van Hagen, L., Petrick, K., Wilhelm, S., & Schmehl, R. (2023). Life-Cycle Assessment of a Multi-Megawatt Airborne Wind Energy System. *Energies*, 16(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16041750>
- Vestas. (2022). *Life Cycle Assessment of Electricity Production from an onshore V150-4.2 MW Wind Plant*.
- Vestas. (2023a). *Life Cycle Assessment of Electricity Production from an onshore V150-6.0 MW Wind Plant*.
- Vestas. (2023b). *Life Cycle Assessment of Electricity Production from an onshore V162-6.2 MW Wind Plant*.
- Vestas. (2024). *Life Cycle Assessment of electricity production from an offshore V236-15 MW wind plant*.
- Villena-Ruiz, R., Ramirez, F. J., Honrubia-Escribano, A., & Gómez-Lázaro, E. (2018). A techno-economic analysis of a real wind farm repowering experience: The Malpica case. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 172, 182–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.07.024>

- Vladimirov, M., Georgiev, G., Aleksieva, R., & Nikolov, T. (2025). *The Kremlin Playbook against Offshore Wind Energy in Bulgaria - Publication - Center for the Study of Democracy*. <https://csd.eu/publications/publication/the-kremlin-playbook-against-offshore-wind-energy-in-bulgaria/>
- Vögele, S., Teja Josyabhatla, V., Ball, C., Rhoden, I., Grajewski, M., Rübhelke, D., & Kuckshinrichs, W. (2023). Robust assessment of energy scenarios from stakeholders' perspectives. *Energy*, 282, 128326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2023.128326>
- Vos, H., Lombardi, F., Joshi, R., Schmehl, R., & Pfenninger, S. (2024). The potential role of airborne and floating wind in the North Sea region. *Environmental Research: Energy*, 1(2), 025002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2753-3751/ad3fbc>
- Waldron, S., Smith, J., Taylor, K., Mcginnes, C., Roberts, N., & McCallum, D. (2018). *Repowering onshore wind farms: a technical and environmental exploration of foundation reuse*. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SCZDE>
- Weidner, T., Galán-Martín, Á., Walbech Ryberg, M., & Guillén-Gosálbez, G. (2022). Energy systems modeling and optimization for absolute environmental sustainability: Current landscape and opportunities. *Computers and Chemical Engineering*, 164, 107883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2022.107883>
- Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., & Weidema, B. (2016). The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): Overview and methodology. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 21(9), 1218–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>
- West, S., & Schill, C. (2022). Negotiating the ethical-political dimensions of research methods: a key competency in mixed methods, inter- and transdisciplinary, and co-production research. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 2022 9:1, 9(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01297-z>
- Wilhelm, S. (2018). Life Cycle Assessment of Electricity Production from Airborne Wind Energy. In *Airborne Wind Energy. Advances in Technology Development and Research* (pp. 727–750). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-1947-0_30
- WindEurope. (2025). *Wind energy in Europe: 2024 Statistics and the outlook for 2025-2030*.
- Ziegler, L., Gonzalez, E., Rubert, T., Smolka, U., & Melero, J. J. (2018). Lifetime extension of onshore wind turbines: A review covering Germany, Spain, Denmark, and the UK. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (Vol. 82, pp. 1261–1271). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.100>
- Zimmermann, T., & Gößling-Reisemann, S. (2011). Optimal repowering of wind energy converters: energy demand and CO₂ intensity as indicators. In *Life Cycle Management*.
- Zografos, C., & Martinez-Alier, J. (2009). The Politics of Landscape Value: A Case Study of Wind Farm Conflict in Rural Catalonia. *Environment and Planning A*, 41(7), 1726–1744. <https://doi.org/10.1068/A41208>

9 ANNEXES

9.1 A NOTE ON AIRBORNE WIND

Airborne wind energy (AWE) is the conversion of wind energy into electricity using tethered flying devices. It has not been examined within this research, as it has its own dedicated WindLab (#3) in WP4. However, literature highlights several aspects relevant for prospective environmental assessments. Compared to conventional wind turbines, AWE requires considerably fewer structural components such as towers and foundations, which reduces overall material demand (e.g., steel, concrete, and rare earths) and simplifies deployment in remote or logistically constrained areas (Coutinho, 2024; van Hagen et al., 2023; Wilhelm, 2018). Life cycle assessments suggest global warming impacts of AWE prototypes to be in a similar range as horizontal-axis wind turbines (van Hagen et al., 2023) and lower than those of solar or diesel-based systems (Coutinho, 2024). In addition, the mobility of AWE allows operation in sites with limited accessibility, while ground-based accessibility of components when not in use may reduce maintenance efforts (Coutinho, 2024). These characteristics have also been associated with positive expectations regarding social acceptance (Schmidt et al., 2022, 2024).

Overall, further research on AWE and its integration into the energy system is encouraged, as explored in WP2 of JW4A (Vos et al., 2024), alongside dedicated assessments of its potential environmental impacts to inform eco-design strategies.

9.2 MATERIALS FOR THE SPANISH CASE STUDY

9.2.1 ELECTRICITY SYSTEM DATA

9.2.1.1 Baseline (2024)

National level (NUTS-0)

Table 9. Spanish annual electricity production per technology in 2024.

Technology	Electricity production (GWh)
Biogas	700
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine	35800
Combined Heat and Power (Biomass)	3000
Combined Heat and Power (Natural Gas)	16400
Waste	2200
Gas turbine	700
Coal	3000
Hydropower (reservoir)	11900
Hydropower (run-of-river)	23000
Electricity import (France)	10106
Electricity import (Morocco)	356

Electricity import (Portugal)	3891
Lignite	0
Nuclear (Pressure Water Reactor)	44500
Nuclear (Boiling Water Reactor)	7900
Oil	3700
Solar Thermal (Parabolic)	4000
Solar Thermal (Tower)	91.0
Solar Photovoltaics	44520.2
Wind (Offshore)	0
Wind (Onshore)	60900

Table 9 presents the annual electricity production used in our baseline 2024 scenario. The primary data source is the Spanish National Grid Operator, Red Eléctrica de España (REE). However, as REE does not distinguish between certain electricity generation technologies, we applied the following assumptions to disaggregate or clarify the data:

- **Hydropower:** We assumed that hydropower production consists of 34% reservoir-based and 66% run-of-river systems. *Data source: Ecoinvent v3.9.1.*
- **Nuclear:** We estimated that 85% of nuclear electricity is produced by Pressurized Water Reactors and 15% by Boiling Water Reactors. *Data source: Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO): <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/energia/nuclear/centrales/espana.html>*
- **Solar Thermal:** We assumed that solar thermal generation consists of 2.2% tower technology and 97.8% parabolic trough technology. *Data source: Ecoinvent v3.9.1.*
- **Other Renewables:** REE groups certain technologies under the category "Other renewables," which we interpreted as including only biomass and biogas. Based on data from the 2019 PNIEC (Table A19), we assumed production shares of 18.8% for biomass and 81.2% for biogas.
- **Co-generation:** As REE does not specify the types of co-generation, we assumed that 100% of the reported co-generation is gas-based.
- **Waste:** We aggregated REE's categories "Renewable Waste" and "Non-Renewable Waste" into a single "Waste" category by summing their reported values.
- **Imports and Exports:** REE reports gross imports, exports, and net balances of electricity with neighboring countries. Although Spain is a net exporter of electricity, we accounted for the reported imports, as they are essential for the operational balance of the electricity network.

Autonomous Community (NUTS-2)

REE provides electricity production data disaggregated by Autonomous Community. To regionalize the data, we applied the same technology split assumptions used in the Baseline 2024 scenario (at the national level, NUTS-0). We acknowledge this introduces a degree of imprecision. For example, a national share of 33% hydropower reservoir does not necessarily imply the same proportion holds

across all regions. Nevertheless, this approach serves as a reasonable proxy in the absence of more detailed, region-specific technology data.

Figure 35. Baseline electricity mix of the Autonomous communities (NUTS 2)

9.2.1.2 PNIEC2023 (2030)

National level (NUTS-0)

Table 10. Spanish annual electricity production per technology in 2030 according to PNIEC2023.

Technology	Electricity production (GWh)
Biogas	2640
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine	20153
Combined Heat and Power (Biomass)	8029
Combined Heat and Power (Natural Gas)	16288
Waste	1698
Gas turbine	0
Coal	0
Hydropower (reservoir)	9779.7
Hydropower (run-of-river)	18984.3
Electricity import (France)	4298
Electricity import (Morocco)	0
Electricity import (Portugal)	9707
Lignite	0
Nuclear (Pressure Water Reactor)	33846.2
Nuclear (Boiling Water Reactor)	1325.8
Oil	3975
Solar Thermal (Parabolic)	11854
Solar Thermal (Tower)	90.9611
Solar photovoltaics	138307
Wind (Offshore)	6289.8
Wind (Onshore)	123812.2

Table 10 presents the annual electricity production used in our PNIEC 2030 scenario. The primary data source is the Spanish National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC2023). However, as PNIEC2023 does not differentiate between certain electricity generation technologies, we applied the following assumptions to disaggregate or clarify the data:

- Nuclear:** Four Spanish nuclear power plants are scheduled to shut down between 2024 and 2030. Among them, *Cofrentes* (a boiling water reactor) and *Ascó* (a pressurized water reactor) are expected to remain operational during 2030. Given that *Cofrentes* is scheduled to close in November, while *Ascó* will cease operations in October, we assume that *Cofrentes* will contribute slightly more electricity production in 2030.
- Solar Thermal:** We assume that all new solar thermal capacity added during the period will be based exclusively on parabolic trough technology, with no new tower installations.

- **Other Technologies:** For all other generation technologies, we apply the same disaggregation assumptions as in the Baseline 2024 scenario.

Autonomous Community (NUTS-2)

The PNIEC2023 does not specify the regional distribution of future infrastructure, providing only a national-level outlook for electricity production. Consequently, we had to downscale the national data to the regional level following the assumption that the regional distribution observed in 2024 will remain constant through 2030. This means, for example, that if Andalucía accounted for 11% of Spain’s wind energy capacity in 2024, we assume it will retain the same share in 2030, albeit applied to a larger total electricity production, given the planned expansion of wind energy. The only exception to this downscaling method is nuclear, for which we do have region-specific data for nuclear phase-outs based on the official Spanish shutdown plan, which we applied directly to the corresponding regions. Finally, as there was no offshore wind in 2024, we had to use a different approach. We took the Spanish officially designated areas and assumed the production would be equally distributed among all of them.

Figure 36. PNIEC Electricity mix of the Autonomous communities (NUTS 2)

Electricity mix in Castilla-La Mancha

Electricity mix in Castilla y León
Solar photovoltaics

Electricity mix in Cataluña

Electricity mix in Comunidad de Madrid

Electricity mix in Comunidad Valenciana

Electricity mix in Extremadura

9.2.1.3 Built infrastructure between 2024 and 2030

In this assessment, we focus exclusively on infrastructure that will be built between 2024 and 2030, as we aim to quantify the environmental impacts associated with the energy transition, not those related to already existing assets.

We consider the addition of new power generation capacity (across all technologies), energy storage systems (both pumped hydro and chemical batteries) (Table 11), and planned transmission lines (Table 12). To estimate the scale of new infrastructure, we calculate the difference between the projected 2030 power capacity and the existing 2024 capacity for each technology. Only technologies with a net positive increase in capacity are included in the analysis (thereby only technologies increasing their capacities).

Table 11. Newly installed power capacity (in MW) in the period 2024-2030 per technology, following PNIEC2023.

Technology	Newly installed power capacity (MW)
Wind (Onshore)	26950.1
Wind (Offshore)	3000
Solar photovoltaics (open ground)	31852.8
Solar photovoltaics (rooftop)	12073.8
Solar Thermal (Parabolic)	2501.9
Biogas	74.4
Biomass	665.2
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine	361.9
Hydropower (Pumped)	1999.6
Battery	13557.5

It is important to note that this analysis does not account for cases of repowering or the substitution of existing infrastructure. While this simplification is appropriate for short-term horizons, it may

underestimate impacts in longer-term assessments, particularly in Spain's case, where the wind energy fleet is relatively aged, with an average turbine age of 14.2 years (the oldest in Europe) and approximately 60% of turbines older than 15 years.

The analysis is performed at the national level (NUTS0). Since most infrastructure-related impacts, apart from those associated with installation, occur offsite, a finer spatial resolution is not used. Higher resolution would require speculative assumptions about the specific location of future infrastructure, introducing unnecessary uncertainty.

Table 12. Newly installed transmission lines (km) in the period 2024-2030, following PNIEC2023.

Technology		Newly installed transmission lines (km)
Alternate Current (Overhead Line)		2981
Direct Current (Subsea Line)		704

9.2.2 LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY DATA

In this section, we explain the life cycle inventory sources used to model each technology, both for the operation and the infrastructure (Table 13). For all the operational inventories, we applied two crucial steps:

- Eliminate the infrastructure input of the inventory. This is because infrastructure impacts are analyzed separately from operational impacts.
- Separate the technosphere (offsite) from the biosphere (onsite). For example, imagine we have an inventory for the production of 1 kWh of electricity from an oil power plant. Let's say it requires X kg of heavy fuel oil (primary energy source) and Y kg of lubricating oil (maintenance). These two inputs are coming from the technosphere (they are manufactured or extracted somewhere in the value chain). These two must be separated from the direct emissions of the oil power plant (e.g., carbon dioxide or methane), which are onsite emissions (biosphere exchanges).

Technologies in green color in the table have special modifications that are explained in the following subsections.

Table 13. Relation between technology and the life-cycle inventory source used to model the operation and the infrastructure. In green, technologies with special modifications.

Technology	Operational LCI source	Infrastructure LCI source
Biogas	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Biomass	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Natural Gas	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Waste	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 apos	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Coal	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Hydro (reservoir)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff (with modifications)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff (with modifications)
Hydro (run-of-river)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff (with modifications)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff (with modifications)
Import (France)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Import (Morocco)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Import (Portugal)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Lignite	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Nuclear (Pressure Water Reactor)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Nuclear (Boiling Water Reactor)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Oil	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Thermosolar (parabolic)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Thermosolar (tower)	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Wind (onshore)	WindTrace (maintenance)	WindTrace (fleet)
Gas turbine	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff	Not included. No new installations
Solar photovoltaics (openground)	No source. We assume its operation does not have any impact	Premise (fleet)
Solar photovoltaics (rooftop)	No source. We assume its operation does not have any impact	Premise (fleet)
Alternate Current (Overhead Line)	No source. We assume its operation does not have any impact	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Direct Current (Subsea Line)	No source. We assume its operation does not have any impact	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Hydropower (Pumped)	No source. It is included in the electricity demand	Ecoinvent v3.9.1 cutoff
Battery	No source. It is included in the electricity demand	Premise (fleet)

9.2.2.1 Hydropower modifications

In *Ecoinvent*, land use flows associated with hydropower are included in the electricity production inventories. However, since it is the infrastructure itself (e.g., the dam or run-of-river power plant) that occupies land, we consider it more appropriate to attribute these flows to the infrastructure inventory. This approach aligns with the treatment of other electricity generation technologies, where land occupation is linked to the physical installation. Therefore, we transferred the land use flows from the hydropower electricity production processes to the corresponding infrastructure processes. To ensure consistency, we rescaled the land use amounts based on the estimated lifetime electricity production of each hydropower infrastructure, as specified in the *Ecoinvent* dataset descriptions.

9.2.2.2 WindTrace

In order to model onshore and offshore wind technologies, we used *WindTrace*. *WindTrace* has been the core work of JustWind4All WP1 Task 1.1 and has been extensively described in Deliverable 1.1. In summary, *WindTrace* is a parametrized life-cycle inventory model, which generates tailor-made life-cycle inventories based on technical parameters defined by users/practitioners. The parameters include turbine power, manufacturer, rotor diameter, hub height, commissioning year, generator type, recycled steel share, lifetime, and end-of-life scenario. In the case of offshore turbines, it allows distinguishing between gravity-based, monopile, tripod, or floating (barge, spar-buoy, semi-sub, or tension-leg platform).

WindTrace allows for the separate modeling of each life-cycle phase. We take advantage of this feature by assigning only the maintenance-related processes to the electricity production inventory (excluding raw material extraction, manufacturing, and other upstream activities). Specifically, the electricity production inventory includes lubricating oil replacements and scheduled maintenance, and inspection visits.

Conversely, the infrastructure inventory encompasses all other life-cycle stages, excluding maintenance. This includes raw material extraction, component manufacturing, transport, installation, and end-of-life processes.

9.2.2.3 Creation of technology fleets (wind, solar photovoltaics, batteries)

Solar photovoltaics, onshore and offshore wind energy, and chemical batteries are expected to have a higher influence on future energy systems after the energy transition. Thus, we decided to treat these four technologies as special cases, creating technology fleets for all of them, where different sub-technologies are included.

Wind

The general approach for wind energy modeling is illustrated in Figure 37, which presents a schematic example of how we construct a representative wind fleet. In this example, we developed inventories for 4 MW and 6 MW onshore wind turbines using *WindTrace*. However, the approach is flexible and can accommodate turbines of any capacity or configuration. Once the capacity shares of each turbine type are defined, the individual inventories generated by *WindTrace* are combined

into a single aggregated inventory representing the wind fleet. This fleet inventory is normalized to a functional unit of 1 MW installed capacity. The same methodology is applied for offshore wind turbines.

For onshore wind, we modelled a fleet composed of 30% 4 MW turbines and 70% 6 MW turbines. These shares are informed by the average turbine size of 5.7 MW for recent and upcoming orders in Europe, as reported by WindEurope (2024 Statistics and the Outlook for 2025–2030, p.33).

For offshore wind, we based our fleet composition on two relevant projects: Parc Tramuntana, a planned wind farm off the northeastern coast of Catalunya, and PLOCAN, an offshore test site in the Canary Islands. We included:

- 14 MW turbines based on the Siemens Gamesa SG 14-222 DD design.
- 15 MW turbines based on the Vestas V236-15.0 MW model, which is likely to be used in Parc Tramuntana.

In terms of foundation types, we assumed a 50/50 split between:

- Floating spar-buoy platforms (50%, representative of Parc Tramuntana)
- Tension-leg platforms (50%, based on the PLOCAN X1 project)

Figure 37. Schema of a wind fleet in ENBIOS.

Solar photovoltaics

Premise (Sacchi et al., 2021) is a prospective life cycle inventory (LCI) database that integrates prospective inventory data on emerging technologies, including photovoltaic systems. The database covers a wide range of PV technologies such as Cadmium Telluride (CdTe), CIS, micro-Si, mono-Si (single-Si), poly-Si (multi-Si), s-Si, ribbon-Si, perovskite-on-silicon, and GaAs. It also distinguishes between types of installation (open ground vs. rooftop/integrated) and includes a variety of system sizes: 3 kWp, 93 kWp, 156 kWp, 280 kWp, 570 kWp, and 1.3 MWp.

For open ground PV systems (Figure 38a), we define the fleet inventory by specifying the technology mix (e.g., shares of CdTe, CIS, micro-Si, mono-Si, poly-Si) directly, creating a weighted average inventory.

For rooftop PV systems (Figure 38b), we adopt a two-step approach. First, we model a representative inventory for each installation size (3 kWp, 93 kWp, 156 kWp, and 280 kWp). These individual inventories are then aggregated into a final 1 MWp rooftop fleet inventory, based on the assumed or observed market share of each system size.

The PV technology shares used in our modeling are based on current market distributions in Spain, as reported in the Informe Anual UNEF 2024 (UNEF, 2024). A summary of this modeling data is included in Table 14, 15 and 16. These shares reflect the most recent trends in PV deployment by technology type and installation size.

Figure 38. Schema of (a) open ground photovoltaics fleet and (b) rooftop photovoltaics fleet in ENBIOS.

Table 14. Modeled Open Ground PV (technology shares)

Technology	Share (%)
CdTe	2%
CIS	0%
micro-Si	0%
multi-Si	1%
single-Si	97%

Table 15. Modeled Rooftop PV (Technology Shares by Installation Size)

Technology	3 kWp	93 kWp	156 kWp	280 kWp
single-Si	97%	98%	98%	98%
multi-Si	1%	2%	2%	2%
CdTe	2%	0%	0%	0%
CIS	0%	0%	0%	0%
a-Si	0%	0%	0%	0%
ribbon-Si	0%	0%	0%	0%

Table 16. Modeled Rooftop PV (Power Share by Installation Size)

System Size	Share of Total Rooftop Capacity (%)
3 kWp	22%
93 kWp	9%
156 kWp	9%
280 kWp	60%

Batteries

Premise additional inventories include several chemical battery technologies (i.e., LFP, NMC111, NMC523, NMC622, NMC811, NMC955, SiB, Vanadium, Lead-acid, and Sodium-Nickel). Moreover, it also provides a battery capacity market, which reflects the idea of battery fleets able to store electricity. This market represents the current market distribution, where lithium batteries (LFPs and NMCs) dominate 80% of the market share.

In our modeling, we assume this current market distribution provided by *premise*, as the timeframe of the analysis is the coming 6 years, for which we do not expect dramatic market trend changes.

9.3 MATERIALS FOR THE BULGARIAN CASE STUDY

9.3.1 DENDROGRAMS FOR THE DEFINITION OF METRICS

Figure 39. Dendrograms for WEM and WAM scenarios

Changes with respect to the DoA	No changes to report
Dissemination and uptake	Public
Short summary of results (<250 words)	<p>This report presents holistic impact assessments of wind energy governance in three European regions—Spain, Portugal, and Bulgaria—using Quantitative Storytelling to ensure relevance. ENBIOS and WindTrace were used for holistic assessment and life cycle impacts.</p> <p>In Spain, the analysis of the 2030 National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) shows that while decarbonization reduces local emissions, it increases upstream pressures such as material extraction and land use. A breakeven analysis reveals that some impacts (e.g., ionising radiation) are offset within a few years, while others (e.g., material resource use) remain uncompensated, highlighting long-term sustainability challenges.</p> <p>In Portugal, the study of the Cabril wind park compares end-of-life strategies: repowering, substitution, and lifetime extension. Repowering boosts electricity output but increases material impacts; extensions reduce impacts but yield less energy, revealing a trade-off between material efficiency and energy productivity.</p> <p>In Bulgaria, two energy scenarios (WEM and WAM) are evaluated using life cycle and uncertainty analyses to support public debate on wind energy deployment. The WAM scenario, featuring higher proportions of wind and solar, results in lower environmental impacts and increased statistical reliability. Wind energy is identified as the most environmentally friendly option, whereas biomass and nuclear energy need to be reconsidered because of their effects on land use, toxicity, and resource utilization.</p> <p>These findings underscore the need for context-sensitive, participatory, and justice-oriented approaches to wind energy governance, emphasizing that sustainability involves navigating trade-offs and addressing both local and global impacts.</p>
Evidence of accomplishment	<p>This deliverable can be found in Zenodo.</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/16991190</p>